

DASTUR-ul-ALBAB

Fi

'ILM-il-HISAB

INTRODUCTION

IN 1943 my attention was drawn by my friend and colleague, Dr. Riazul Islam, to a manuscript entitled *Dasturul Albab fi 'Ilm-il-Hisab*, a Persian manuscript in the Rampur State Library, Rampur. This book was listed along with other books on Arithmetic, but on closer scrutiny it was found that *Dasturul Albab* contained some very important chapters on the taxes which a Muslim ruler could levy according to *shari'at*, and others which were permitted by custom ; a glossary of revenue terms and other technical terms which a *Muharrir* (clerk) was required to know, being necessary for the discharge of his duties ; an exceedingly useful chapter on the method of maintaining registers in the revenue departments, and the qualifications and functions of the different officials connected with the Ministry of Revenue. This book is all the more valuable as there are very few treatises dealing with the system of revenue administration obtaining during the Sultanate period. The book was written by one Haji Abdul Hamid Muharrir Ghaznavi for the use of his son Ruknuddin. Haji Abdul Hamid says in the Introduction that there are two categories of sciences, one being the science of matter or bodies and the other that of religion. The knowledge of Mathematics is, however, indispensable for both these sciences. In the year 734 A. H. when he was 44 years of age it occurred to him to write a book for his son Ruknuddin Abul Fateh Ahmad. In the course of his advice to his son he draws his attention to the intricacies of the science of Mathematics and how to comprehend the same. He gives a computation as to how one grain of barley multiplies into one maund of barley in the course of nine years. In the year 760 A. H. when the author was 917 months old *i. e.* (76 years and 5 months) he wrote this book and named it *Dasturul Albab fi 'Ilmi'l Hisab*. His age as mentioned here differs by six years as mentioned by him elsewhere in his book. He probably started writing the book in the year 734 A. H. and completed it in 760 A. H. The book was intended to be dedicated to Hazrat Nizamuddin Aulia in the year 721 A. H. but as its compilation was undertaken in 734 A. H. this presumably could not be done (Fol. 76b). The author further refers to having written the book during the reign of Firoz Shah during the Wizarat of Khan-i-Jahan, the Wazir of that Sultan (Fol. 45). He also refers to Ahmad Ayaz Khan-i-

Jahan, the wazir of Muhammad bin Tughlaq. From the internal evidence it appears that Haji Abdul Hamid Ghaznavi started compiling this book during the time of Muhammad bin Tughlaq and finished it in the time of Firoz Shah. The name of the scribe cannot be determined as the manuscript is incomplete towards the end. It is written in Khat-e-Bahari and covers 129 leaves, the size of each page being 10"x5 $\frac{3}{4}$ ". From the calligraphy and the condition of the paper it may be conjectured that the manuscript belongs to the 15th or, at the latest, the 16th century of the Christian era. The first 33 leaves of the manuscript are mutilated and suffer from frequent and lengthy lacunae. In the later portions the lacunae are less frequent and shorter.

The book is divided into five parts or books, further sub-divided into 32 chapters and 177 sections. The following are the contents of the first part of the work.

Part I : Terms employed by the revenue officials and is divided into four chapters :

Chapter I : Terms employed by the revenue and account clerks ;

Chapter II : The sources of revenue including the *shara'i* taxes and extra-*shara'i* taxes ;

Chapter III : The various registers which are maintained in the revenue department and the method of recording entries in the same ;

Chapter IV : The qualifications and functions of the officers connected with the Ministry of Revenue. This Chapter is further sub-divided into six sections:

Section I : Qualifications of the Wazir

Section II : " " Mushrif

Section III : " " Mustaufi

Section IV : " " Barid

Section V : " " Nazir

Section VI : " " Waqf

This is the most important portion of the book the translation of which is presented in this article. On account of the mutilated condition of the manuscript and the numerous lacunae a verbatim translation has not been possible. Dr. Ishtiaq Husain Quraishi, who borrowed a copy of the manuscript from me, used the material in this chapter in preparation of the second edition of his valuable book Administration of the Sultanate of Delhi and made the following observations about its value :

"I also owe a debt of gratitude to my friend Shaikh Abdur Rashid, Lecturer in History in the Muslim University, Aligarh, who brought to my notice Dastur-ul-albab fi ilm-il-hisab, a manuscript in the Rampur State Library. This work is of invaluable importance for the students of the agrarian and revenue administration of Firuz Shah's reign. The author is Haji Abdul Hamid Muharrir Ghaznavi who finished the book in 760 A. H. He had planned the work in 734 A. H. ; hence there can be little doubt that he was familiar with the

administration of the previous reign as well. His descriptions of the various institutions and their working as well as his glossary of technical terms are most illuminating. Shaikh Abdur Rashid not only drew my attention to this important work, he also lent me the transcriptions made for him in instalments as he received them and the references in this treatise are to his copy. It was very fortunate indeed that I came to know of this manuscript at a stage when I could use it in this edition."

I have received valuable assistance in preparing the translation of this part of the book from Dr. Riazul Islam, Mr. Azizur Rahman, Maulana Abrar Husain Farooqi and Mr. Khaliq Ahmad Nizami, to whom I tender my grateful thanks.

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PART I: CHAPTER II

A DESCRIPTION OF THE TAXES FOR BAIT-UL-MAL, THE COLLECTION OF WHICH IS SANCTIONED BY SHARI'AH

The scribe should know that there are certain taxes, which are sanctioned by *Shari'ah* and custom, and others that were levied in the time of the earlier rulers. Such taxes are twenty in number.

Be it known that the taxes sanctioned by the *Shari'ah* are eleven in number : 1. the *Zakat*; 2. '*Ushr* on land, and *Kharaj* on crops and fruits of trees, and *ijarat* and *musaqat* (reclamation) of dead lands; 3. *Jiziyah* on *zimmis* who are *ahl-e-kitab*; 4. *Khums* on booty; 5. Income from tribute which is levied from the *ahl-e-harb*; 6. Presents which the *ahl-e-harb* tender to the Muslim ruler; 7. Plunder from lands²; 8. *Khums* on (income from) mines and treasure-troves; 9. Tax on intestate property which ought to be protected; 10. '*Ushr* which is levied from non-Muslims living in Muslim lands; 11. *Khums* (one-fifth) which is levied on what is taken out of the rivers, such as ambergris, corals and pearls, and other articles of the same kind.

There are two other sources of income which become part of the legal taxes. Firstly, goods which are recovered from the highway robbers, taxes introduced and levied during the time of the earlier rulers amongst which are included *baj*, tax on brokers, tax on (various) occupations and *bahila* which is levied from merchants at the outposts and on highways; secondly, tax on craftsmen, and *zaraib*³ and tax on wine, *bagnia*⁴ and *bhang*, the rate of which varies from country to country. These are the various taxes.

1. *A Description of the Zakat Taxes*⁵: This (*zakat*) is determined by *Shari'ah*

according to (the valuation of) property and is fixed by God (may His name be hallowed!) on all Muslims who are major, and in full senses, and possess the legal minimum (*nisab*). *Nisab*⁶ (property) should be free from debt, and a year should have elapsed over it ; and this (*zakat*) is of two kinds : one on property which is hidden, and the other (on property) which is apparent.

Tax on property that is apparent is tax on quadrupeds that always graze in the plains and pastures ; the tax on hidden property is tax on gold and silver and on articles and commodities of commerce. Regarding the payment of *zakat* on non-apparent property, the practice in the time of Amir-ul-Mominin 'Uthman⁷ was that he (payer) was permitted to disburse it himself and he might not pay (the same) to *bait-ul-mal*.

The *zakat* on quadrupeds is this : on all such animals which have grazed for a year or more and those which have been grazing for six months or less than six months, on them *zakat* does not accrue. Of quadrupeds there are four kinds which are liable to (the payment of) *zakat* ; first are camels ; second, sheep ; third, cattle ; and fourth, horses.

Of camels : For five camels one goat is the tax that should be paid ; for ten camels two goats ; for fifteen camels three goats ; for 20 camels four. When the number twentyfive is reached, a one year old camel becomes due and the same upto the number thirtyfive ; and when the number reaches thirtysix, two years old camel should be given, upto the time when the number reaches ninetyone ; when the number reaches ninetytwo, two camels, each one year old, falls due, upto when the number reaches one hundred and twenty. This tax is according to the above schedule. For every five camels above this number two camels, one year old, and one goat should be given.

Zakat on goats : *Zakat* is not due on goats unless the number exceeds thirtynine ; when the number reaches forty, one goat is due and the same upto when the number exceeds one hundred and twentyone, when two goats become due till the number reaches two hundred ; when the number reaches two hundred and one, three goats as *zakat* fall due and that upto the extent when the number exceeds three hundred ; and upto four hundred, four goats fall due ; and after that for every hundred goats, the payer should give one goat as *zakat*. The rule of *zakat* for goats and sheep is the same. If the female is a doe and the male he-goat, and there is an offspring, in this case regard should be paid to the female, for the child follows the mother as is the rule regarding the free man or the slaves. If the mother is a she-goat it should be included amongst the goats, and is liable to *zakat* ; if it is a doe *zakat* is not due.

Zakat on cows and buffaloes : *Zakat* on cows and buffaloes which are pastured does not accrue unless the number twentynine is exceeded. When

the number reaches thirty, one year old cow falls due as is related of the Prophet who directed *Mu'az Ibn Jabal*⁸ thus when he sent him to Yemen: "Levy on every thirty cows one male or female calf in the second year, and for every forty cows one year old calf." Over every thirtyone cows and buffaloes upto the number forty, one he-calf or she-calf in the second year falls due. Beyond forty, for every excess there are two traditions from *Imam Azam Abu Hanifa*⁹ (may God be pleased with him!). According to one report when the number 41 is reached *zakat* equal to one fourth of 'Ushr (2½%) of a year-old-calf is added. When the number exceeds forty-one, half of 'Ushr (5%) becomes due, and the rate remains the same till the number 60 is reached. When the number is sixty, 2 calves two years old are due. According to the second report, nothing accrues after forty till the number is exceeded by ten. When it is fifty, one year old calf falls due. After that there is no addition upto 59. When the number sixty is reached, two year old calves become due, and (the scribe should) calculate the rest on this basis.

About Zakat on horses: In the case of pastured horses, when males and females are together *zakat* becomes due. The owner has the option of paying 1 *dinar*¹⁰ for every horse or to appraise their value and pay 5 *dirhams*¹¹ for every 200 *dirhams*. If the horses are all male, nothing accrues according to *Imam Azam* (may God be pleased with him!) for male horses yield no offspring. According to a second report no *zakat* is due on horses.

On pastured camels and donkeys no *zakat* accrues unless they are, intended for sale.

'Ushr¹² :- 'Ushr is of two kinds : firstly, 'ushr on crops ; secondly 'ushr on articles of merchandise, and all that is taken out for sale.

'Ushr on crops and fruits: Whatever grows on 'ushri land, 'ushr becomes due on the same. 'Ushr land is of five kinds :

1. All *harbi* land is 'ushri land.
2. Land captured by force by a Muslim ruler and distributed amongst the Muslim soldiers is also 'ushri land.
3. Lands situated in the territory of the *ahl-e-harb*, if the lands belong to the Muslims and the distance between the two is such as can be covered in one night or a day or less.
4. *Dead Land*¹³ which is reclaimed by a Muslim with the sanction, of the ruler, and the land that adjoins other 'ushri land is also 'ushri land, but if it adjoins *Kharaji* land, such land is also *Kharaji* land.

5. If a Muslim lays out a garden on his land or cultivates it with water from a river near by and which is not owned by anybody such as the Oxus and Euphrates and others besides these, land near these rivers will be 'ushri land and double the 'ushr becomes due from the occupier. And on land which is irrigated by buckets or by animals then half 'ushr is due and this because the owner has to undergo much labour in irrigating it. And what-

ever grows on the land, like wood, flowers, or other things, on all of them 'ushr is due. If honey is found on 'ushri land, 'ushr becomes due because the bees are like trees and honey is like its fruit. The land of the *mukatabs*¹⁴ is subject to 'ushr. If anybody sells 'ushri land or *kharaji* land, the *kharaj* becomes due as under :-

If such period of the year remains during which cultivation is not possible, 'ushr or *kharaj* will be due from the seller. If *rabi*¹⁵ crop can be sown so as to become ripe, 'ushr or *kharaj* will be paid by the buyer; if *rabi* crop cannot be sown, 'ushr or *kharaj* will be paid by the seller. If the land is returned by the *ajir*, according to *Sahibain*¹⁶ the 'ushr is due from the seller; if any person takes 'ushr land on lease and cultivates it, 'ushr on that land is due from the lessee. If a Musalman buys *kharaji* land then that land still remains *kharaji* land and *kharaj* is due from the owner.

2. 'Ushr on articles of trade : If a merchant, Muslim or *harbi*, passes a collector of 'ushr, the 'ashir (collector of 'ushr) should collect one fourth of 'ushr ($2\frac{1}{2}\%$) from Muslims and $\frac{1}{2}$ of 'ushr (5%) from *zimmis* and from a *harbi* according to what has been agreed upon. Nothing should be levied from *mukatabs* (slaves) from amongst the *harbis* or the partner of a slave because the latter is not the owner of property but a mere agent like a permitted slave. If a merchant passes an *ashir* and he has articles which will perish if not sold within two days, then according to Imam Azam Abu Hanifa (may God be pleased with him!) 'ushr does not become due, for it does not last for one year. According to the *Sahibain*, he (*ashir*) should charge 'ushr.

3. *Khumus-i-Ghanaim*¹⁷ :- The jurists differ as to the nature of *ghanimah* and *fay*¹⁸. Whatever the Musalmans capture from the infidels by force and assault, (such as) *dirhams*, *dinars* and other articles of value are termed *ghanimah*; and houses and other buildings and lands are called *fay*. *Khwaja Sufyan Thawri* (may God be merciful to him!) says that whatever Muslims capture from infidels by force and assault is called *ghanimah* and whatever is taken by agreement is called *fay*. The *Wazir* should collect and guard all articles, animate and inanimate, articles small or large and should set apart *khums* and *radhkh*¹⁹. The rest should be deposited in the *bait-ul-mal*. The *radhkh* should be paid to the legal recipients of *radhkh*. The recipients of *radhkh* are firstly, the slaves of the soldiers who have taken part in battle against the infidels with the permission of their masters; secondly, females who have looked after the general interest of the soldiers and have nursed the wounded on the battlefield; thirdly, the *zimmis*; to all these three groups the ruler grants *radhkh*. *Radkh* means a pittance which is smaller than the legal share (*sahm*).

Of those who have fought against the infidels, the foot soldier is entitled to one share, and the mounted soldier to two shares—one share for the horse according to Imam Abu Hanifa (may God be pleased with him!) and Imam Hasan²⁰ and *Zufar*²¹. According to *Sahibain* every mounted soldier is entitled to 3 shares—one for the horseman and two for his horse

In case of one who has two horses, his share should be increased (proportionately). The Turkish and Arab horses are equal as regards their share. If in a battle a person has a camel, or beast of burden or donkey he is like a foot soldier and his (share) is equal to that of a foot soldier. If a merchant follows the army, and fights side by side with the soldiers, he should be given a share equal to that of a soldier. If a person hires a servant for personal services and he fights along with the soldiers he should be given a share and his wages are cancelled. If during a battle the horse (of a soldier) is killed or wounded so that the soldier is left without a mount, or the enemy captures it (the horse) from him and he has to fight on foot, the same rule will apply to him as to a mounted soldier. If a person joins the battle where he has no need for the horse, in that case too the share of a mounted soldier should be given to him, and to the foot soldier the share of a foot soldier.

In the distribution of spoils the king has the discretion either to distribute (*ghanaim*) in the *dar-ul-harb* or in the *dar-ul-Islam*²². If one of the soldiers dies before his return from the *dar-ul-harb* or dies after his return from the *dar-ul-harb*, in that case his heirs will get his share at the time of the distribution (of the *ghanaim*). If the king makes an announcement which is permissible on the precedent that in the battle of *Badr*²³ the Prophet (peace be on him!) had announced "whosoever kills an unbeliever, whatever belonged to the slain will now belong to him (slayer) and the soldier who captures somebody, the captive shall be his slave"—whatever (belongs) to the slain person (like) horse, camel or cash is called *sabb* ; all that should be given to the slayer.

4. KHUMS ON RIQAZ AND MINES²⁴

Treasure Troves and Mines : Whatever is taken out of the earth is of two kinds. Firstly, that which is taken from under the ground, and has been buried there is called *kanz* (treasure). Secondly, what is obtained from the earth and has been in existence from the day the earth was created, these are known as mines.

Treasures, however, are only of two kinds, one found on land owned by a private individual or public land, and the latter is either desert or pasture land or hills and the same rules apply to both. But whatever is found on *'ushri* lands or *kharaji* lands, we should see whether it bears a sign of Islam ; and the signs of Islam are that the treasure consists of coins coined by a Muslim King or there are papers or books buried near it. The law about such a find is that the discoverer is not entitled to them ; he should make the fact of his find known. If for one year the owner is not found or the finder becomes destitute, he may utilise it for his own purpose or give it away to *darweshes*. This is permissible. If the treasure bears no sign of Islam, one fifth becomes the share of the king and four fifth that of the finder, whether he be a free man or a slave or male or female, Muslim or *zimmi*²⁵. If treasure is found on the land owned by some one then find becomes his (the owner's) property according to *Imam Azam*,

but according to *Imam Yusuf*²⁶ it will belong to the finder.

Regarding mines of gold, silver, iron, tin, lead, etc., *khums* is due on their yield. Regarding mines of precious stones, like rubies, turquoise and emeralds which cannot be melted *khums* is not due. Whatever is taken from rivers, such as ambergris, coral, pearls, etc., according to *Imam Azam Abu Hanifa* *khums* is not due as the rivers do not belong to anybody. According to *Abu Yusuf*, *khums* is due. If two persons set out together to find a treasure and one of them finds it, the whole of it belongs to the finder. If a person hires a labourer to take out a treasure from a pit, whatever is found belongs to the hirer. If a Muslim or a *zimmi* discovers a mine in his house, according to *Imam Azam* (may God be pleased with him!) *khums* is due and should be paid as "the proprietary rights of a Musalman do not lapse in land in any way."

*Kharaj*²⁷: *Kharaj* is the tax which one pays on his land. *Kharaji* land is of five kinds. The first kind is that land which a king captures by force or assault and settles the land upon them (the vanquished). The ruler should fix *kharaj* on the land and levy *jiziyah* on every person settled on that land. If *kharaj* and *jiziyah* are levied together (as one tax) this is also permissible but (the ruler) should distinguish the two as to how much was on account of *kharaj* and how much on account of *jiziyah*. Secondly, when a *zimmi* converts his house into a garden or cultivated field and irrigates the same with *kharaji* water, that land too becomes *kharaji*. Thirdly, if a *zimmi* reclaims dead land with the permission of the ruler, and irrigates it with *kharaji* water that land too becomes *kharaji* land; fourthly, all lands which are irrigated by a canal dug and prepared with the money from *bait-ul-mal* and brought under cultivation, that too becomes *kharaji* land. Fifthly, when *'ushri* land is purchased from a *zimmi* that land becomes *kharaji* land. According to *Imam Azam* (may God be pleased with him!) and *Abu Yusuf* *khums* becomes due on it. According to *Imam Muhammad*²⁸ that land becomes *'ushri* land and according to *Imam Shafi*²⁹ and *Imam Malik*³⁰ the sale (of such land) is void.

Kharaj on lands: This is of two kinds. One is *Kharaj-i-Muqatiah* and the other is *Kharaj-i-Muqassima*.

Kharaj-i-Muqatiah: *Amir-ul Mominin 'Umar*³¹ conquered Kufa and the lands of the people of Kufa were left in their possession and (he first) fixed the *Kharaj*. On every *jarib* of land which was fit for cultivation (he fixed) one standard *dirham* equal in weight to 70 *mithqal* and a *mithqal* is equal to one *Qafiz-e-Hashmi* like the *Sa'a*³² which the Prophet fixed. And on every *jarib* of 33 land which was more fertile he fixed 5 *dirhams* and on every *jarib* of garden land he fixed 10 *dirhams*, and the area of one *jarib* was equal to 60 local yards by 60 local yards. The local yard is longer than one closed fist. The *jarib* is 3600 local yards, and one *Sa'a* is equal to 8 *ratl*.

It is legal to assess *kharaj* on land which cannot bear the burden of

this taxation, at a lower rate because this rate has come down from Amir-ul-Mominin 'Umar who fixed it on such lands as were irrigated from big rivers and much labour was not involved in its cultivation. On the other hand if land is irrigated by wells, much labour has to be borne and the extra labour demands decrease in *kharaj*. The tax fixed by Amir-ul-Mominin 'Umar (may God be pleased with him!) would not be increased. According to *Sahibain* (may God be merciful to them!) the tax may be increased if the land can bear the burden (of it). Imam Abul Qasim was asked: "If there were lands in a village on some of which a low rate of *kharaj* was levied while on other a high rate, was it permissible or not, if the Imam desired, to equalise the tax?" He replied, "Unless the conditions were known under which the amount of *kharaj* on that village was fixed in the first instance and the reason of this difference was known, equalisation of taxes is not permitted and (the rate) should be left as it was."

Kharaj-i-Muqassima : *Kharaj-i-Muqassima* is the *kharaj* which the ruler levies from year to year. This is less than $\frac{1}{2}$ of the produce, such as $\frac{1}{3}$, $\frac{1}{4}$ or $\frac{1}{5}$ and so on. They (the payers) should distribute the burden of it among themselves. If the owner leaves the *kharaj* land uncultivated then the *kharaj* is not remitted; if the owner of land absconds, the ruler should give that land to some one else on the same rate as in the case of the original *kharaj* payer. If *kharaji* land is submerged under water, until the water is drained away, or the crops are destroyed as a result of which there is no yield, the tax on that land is remitted. The same applies to the '*ushr*' land. If the owner gives the land on lease and the crops on that land are damaged, (the labourer's) wages do not lapse and the loss is borne by the owner. If the *kharaj* is in arrears from the owner of the land and he cannot pay on account of poverty, and because of poverty is unable to cultivate or build (on it) and the land is left uncultivated, the king may give that land to some one on lease and levy the *kharaj* from the lessee and the difference (between the income and the tax) should be paid to the owner of the land. If the land is not taken by anyone on lease he may sell that land to a person who is in a position to pay the *kharaj*.

5. *Jiziyah*³⁴: *Jiziyah* is the *kharaj* which is levied on the person of an infidel to the extent which is fixed by stipulation and mutual agreement and consent and that is *kharaj-e-muqassima*. The second kind is that which the ruler fixes by force and compulsion as *jiziyah* according to the rules of *Shari'ah* and that is 12 *dirhams* every year on working men of limited means; on the middle class 24 *dirhams*, and on the well-to-do 48 *dirhams*. A well-to-do person is one who is *sahib-e-nisab*³⁵, that is, who has 200 *dirhams*, and the *darwesh* is one who is not *sahib-e-nisab*. According to some (jurists) whoever can earn by labour so much as would suffice him and his family and who can save something, such a person is well-to-do. And whoever earns so much as would suffice him and his family but cannot save anything such a one is a man of average means. And he, whose

earnings do not suffice him and his family, is a *darwesh*. In every country *kharaj* is fixed differently. *Jiziyah* is not levied from indigent non-muslims, old men, children, the blind, the aged and the disabled and the poor who cannot work and slaves too, because the slave's master pays the *jiziyah*. If it is realised from him it would mean that the master has to pay twice. If the *zimmi* dies, the *jiziyah* is cancelled, but the *kharaj* continues. The *jiziyah* is to be levied from the People of the Scripture and the Magians.

6. Tribute by Agreement : It is of two kinds. The first kind is like the treaty which the Prophet entered into with the tribe of Najran³⁶. And it is like this. If the *ahl-e-harb* humbly and in distress come to the ruler of the Muslims and supplicate protection for their own benefit and in return stipulate to pay the tribute, and the ruler finds it expedient to give them protection, and enters into an agreement for a stipulated amount, that is permissible, as the Prophet entered into an agreement with the people of Najran, who were Christians of Arabia, on condition of payment of 2000 robes every year, 1000 to be paid in the month of Rajab and 1000 in the month of Muharram. *Hilla* means one *izar* and one *rida* or a single piece of cloth which may suffice for both. The second kind is that by which Amir-ul-Mominin 'Umar (may God be pleased with him!) entered into an agreement with Banu Tughlab³⁷. Banu Tughlab were Arab Christians living on the frontiers of *Rum*.³⁸ Amir-ul-Mominin 'Umar (may God be pleased with him!) invited them to Islam. They refused this also. They said, "We are Arabs and it is humiliating for us to pay *jiziyah*. If you levy *jiziyah* from us, we will leave this place and migrate and join your enemies. Otherwise charge from us as you do from the Muslims, that is *zakat*, and we are prepared to pay twice as much as the Muslims do and accept (the same) voluntarily and willingly." Amirul Mominin 'Umar (may God be pleased with him!) thought over it. Qardus bin Daud was a Tughlabi who was acting as an intermediary in this affair and carried on the negotiations. He said "O Amir-ul-Mominin! It is advisable to come to an agreement." The Amir-ul-Mominin consulted others and found that they advised acceptance of the offer. They agreed to charge twice as much (from them) as from Muslims. The Caliph later remarked : "Verily, this is *jiziyah* or *kharaj* on land." The advisability of such a measure shall be determined by the rulers and the owners of the land.

7. Tribute which is taken from the *ahl-e-harb* :—It is this. The infidels avoid fighting and, in order to escape from war, agree to pay tribute and fix the period during which the Muslim army will not attack them. There are two rules for this. If the Muslim army has encamped in their land, whatever money they pay should be regarded as *ghanimah* ; and if the Muslim army had not invaded their land and they despatched messengers, it will be regarded as *jiziyah*. Whatever cash, or presents and offerings the *ahl-e-harb*³⁹ send to the Muslim king from time to time, and agree to enlist themselves amongst the subject people, that also is to be regarded as *jiziyah*.

8. *Khums on the produce of mines* : It is this. Whatever is obtained from mines, one fifth of it belongs to the ruler, and that is regarded as *ghanimah*.

9. *Mal-i-Tarkah* : This is the money realised from the property of a person who dies and leaves no heir. That property is to be handed over to the *bait-ul-mal* ; or if a woman dies and leaves only her husband and has no other heir, whatever is the share of the husband is given to him and the rest is to be paid into the *bait-ul-mal*.

10. 'Ushr^{39A} :—the tax that is levied from the non-Muslim merchants in Muslim lands : It is this. Ami-rul-Mominin 'Umar (may God be pleased with him!) ordered his officers during his *khilafat* to levy 1/2 of 'ushr (5%) from the *zimmi* merchants and 1/4 of 'ushr (2½%) from Muslim merchants. Taxes of this kind were termed in old times as *baj*, and the statement about them will be recorded along with the *muhdas*⁴⁰ taxes. And this kind of 'ushr tax is of the category of *jiziyah* and *kharaj*.

11. There are (two other taxes) : firstly, the property which is captured from the highway robbers and thieves by force, belongs to the owner. No one has any right to it. It should be handed over to the owner except in the case where there is neither the claimant nor any heir and the person from whom it was taken cannot be determined. In that case it should be deposited in the *bait-ul-mal*.

12. Secondly, the fines that were imposed upon thieves and other criminals as punishment so that they might not again repeat the offence. This tax is permitted by the *Shari'ah*. It has been related by others that the ruler may, whenever he finds it proper or expedient, fine persons who have been guilty of a crime or have committed an offence and, therefore, have become liable to fine. The aim of legal punishment is to deter (persons) from committing offences. There are many persons who are not deterred by a corporal punishment or imprisonment, but are deterred and distressed if required to pay fines.

The taxes introduced by the ancient rulers are of three kinds :

A. The first are the *baj* taxes which are levied from merchants at various—stages and outposts and should not exceed this. The writer has heard this from Khwaja Asad that once an elderly person was asked as to what *baj* was and what was its nature. He replied that in olden times the *ashirs* who were appointed by the kings to various highways and outposts for the collection of *zakat* and 'ushr, the same being 1/2 of 'ushr in case of *zimmi*s and *harbi* merchants (and, 1/4 in case of) Muslims, used to charge more than the fixed rate. The reason of this additional charge was that the merchants were afraid of highway robbers on certain dangerous highways and they agreed to pay the *ashirs* (the additional tax) as gratification, and requested them to provide them escort so that they might cross the dangerous parts

without fear. As time passed this practice was repeated from year to year and sometimes (this tax had to be paid) twice or three times a year. From one outpost to the other it was extended and became customary till it became for them a source of perplexity. The *ashirs* could not appropriate this big sum and found it expedient to inform the *diwan* and the ruler. Orders were issued that the *ashirs* should continue the practice, and charge as usual and record it in registers. In the beginning the merchants paid it willingly, but ultimately the king levied it by force and named this as *baj*. This is one of the customary taxes.

B. *Secondly, the tax on sales (bayya'i) brokerage, and tax on artisans.* As righteousness and honesty had decreased and avarice had increased by lapse of time after the Prophet (peace be on him!), and by the time of the later rulers, the traders had given up righteousness, and honest middlemen had become extinct, and merchants were accused of taking usurious profits, and craftsmen became dishonest and notorious for breaches of promise so that what was worth ten *dirham* was sold for twenty. The rulers accused them of this. Perforce they were subjected to a tax and something was realised from them.

C. *Thirdly, khums on what is taken out of the river such as pearls, ambergris, coral, etc. :* According to the theologians nothing is due on what is taken out of the rivers, yet 1/5th (*khums*) is levied on it.

Taxes which are permissible by the Shari'ah and custom for the diwan of the king : In the matter of collection of (these) taxes, proper care should be exercised, and the entire yield and realisations should be recorded by the scribe. He should write down the different items in detail and should take proper care in their disbursement, so that they may not be spent without reason or be wasted. He should realise only the share of the *diwan*, for he will be responsible to God, and on the day of judgment the complainant will make a demand on him, for he was a trustee and they had put reliance on his entries.

*Ijara : Ijara*⁴¹ is a contract for consideration. It is the ownership of some benefit for some consideration. Every *ijara* creates a consideration for both the parties and that which is formed without a consideration is a (case of) lending. *Ijara* is not legal unless it creates mutual consideration. The Prophet has said "Whoever hires a labourer, we shall make him pay his wages;" and whatever contract is made its consideration, its period and the nature of the work should be specified. For example, a house or place for residence, or land for cultivation, and horses or beasts of burden for riding or driving and others like it which are hired for use, may be had by contract in return for a stipulated amount and the purpose thereof should also be specified. For example, if (the services of) a man are hired for tailoring or dyeing clothes or if he is hired so that (he) may carry goods to a place,

or if any person rents a shop and house for residence and does not state as to what work will be done in that place, he may reside there in whatever capacity he likes and may engage in any trade he likes but that of an iron-smith or a butcher or baker as the building is likely to be damaged by the reason of these occupations.

It is not lawful to rent land for cultivation unless it is specified (in the contract) as to what (crop) will be cultivated therein, and unless he makes it a condition with the tenant that he can cultivate whatever he likes; and if land is taken for cultivation on this condition that only one kind of crop will be sown, in that case only one kind of crop will be permitted to be sown. Similarly, if that kind of crop has not been cultivated which was stipulated and another kind of crop is cultivated, if by the crop which was not stipulated lesser damage has been done to the land than what would have resulted from the (cultivation of the) stipulated crop, such contract is valid. If that land had suffered greater damage by the crop which was not stipulated, in that case the damage will have to be made good by the lessee. If the land is rented on condition that any crop might be cultivated such a contract is valid. The lessee should not plant trees on that land, and if he cuts down trees on that land he will be responsible for the same.

If a person hires a house or a dwelling place and fixes the rent for the year at 10 *dirhams* and does not specify as to how much rent is to be paid every month, (such contract) is valid. If a man rents land for purposes of cultivation for a definite period, it is valid. Renewal (of contract) every year is not necessary. If at the time of the contract the period is fixed and if during that period the rent remains the same and is neither higher nor lower than what it was at the time of the contract, this is valid. If the rent is increased (during that period), the tenant may cancel the contract, and may renew the contract according to the (value of) the land and fix the rent. If a piece of land or a house is given on rent for a stipulated period and before the expiry of the period, the rent of a similar land or house (increases), he (the owner) may cancel the contract. He can compel (payment) for the expired (period) according to the stipulated rate of rent and may renew the contract at an enhanced rate for the remaining period. But if the rent of a piece of land or of a house remains the same (the lessor) cannot cancel it during the period (of contract). If the lessor or the lessee dies before the completion of the contract, the contract is null and void by reason of the death, except when the contract is completed and the parties agree to continue it. If a man hires a house or a dwelling place and an enemy (takes adverse possession) of that house and the former hands over the house (to him) or vacates the land and hands it over to him and meanwhile the period of contract expires, or if the hirer, on account of some prohibition from the king, is unable to live in that house or to cultivate that land, the ejection of the hirer is optional. If he wishes he can keep it on the same terms or if he wishes he can decrease the rent. But if he consents (to keep it even) with this defect and utilises it, he cannot decrease the rent afterwards and the entire rent becomes due from him. If a man has a partner-

ship with a person in a house or (a piece of) land and the former rents his portion, this is permissible. If a man hires a house or a dwelling place from two persons, this (too) is permissible. If one of the parties to the contract dies, the share of the partner, who is still alive, is not cancelled. If a man hires a piece of land and takes possession thereof and then rents it to some one else, it is permissible. If the rent is of a nature different from the first, for instance, if the first is in terms of cash and the second is in terms of clothes, if the latter (exceeds the first in valuation), it is not lawful for him. If the first rent is in terms of money and the second rent is also in terms of money, this even is permissible. In this case the excess which he receives from the second kind of rent will not be lawful for him. If a man hands over a (piece of) cloth to a tailor on condition that he should cut it only if that cloth is sufficient for a shirt, otherwise he should leave it as it is, and the tailor cuts that cloth and a shirt can not be made out of it, the tailor is liable to pay the damages.

MUZARIAH⁴²

The validity of *muzariah* depends on (the fulfilment of) certain conditions. One of these is this that the land should be cultivable ; secondly, the period (for which it is leased) should be specified ; thirdly, the person who supplies the seed should be specified ; fourthly, he who does not supply the seed, his share from the yield should be specified ; fifthly, the owner of land should lease the land to the tenant ; sixthly, the kind of seed (to be used) should be specified, so that he may not sow whatever he likes.

There are six kinds of *muzariah*, of which four are valid and two are invalid. The valid kinds are : 1. Where the land and the seed belong to one person and labour and animals to the other. 2. Where land is (supplied) by one and labour, animals and seeds by the other. 3. Where land and animals are supplied by one party and seed and labour by the other. In this case *muzariah*, according to Abu Yusuf, is valid, but according to the apparent meaning of the tradition, this is not correct. There are two (other cases) which are invalid. Firstly, where the land and the oxen and labour are supplied by one and the seed by the other ; secondly, where the seed and the oxen are supplied by one and labour and land by the other. In both these cases *muzariah* is invalid. The proceeds will belong to the man who supplies the seed ; according to one tradition and according to another report, to the owner of the land. The proceeds will be in the possession of the owner of the land as a debt, so that he should pay to the supplier of the seed a portion out of the proceeds. If it was agreed that the owner of the land and the *muzariah* will each receive a certain number of *qafiz* from the yield, such as ten or twenty *qafiz*, such *muzariah* will be void, for it is just possible that the total yield may be just equal to that quantity. If the condition is that the owner of the seeds will take from the yield (the quantity of seeds supplied) and whatever is left will be divided equally between them, the *kharaj* fixed by the ruler on the land will be paid first and whatever is left will be divided amongst them half and half. Such a

muzariah will also be void for the reason stated above for the yield may just cover the quantity (equal to seed supplied).

If they have agreed that the grain will be divided amongst them either half and half, or $\frac{1}{3}$ to the one and two third to the other, and no mention is made of the husk, such a *muzariah* is valid. The husk will belong to the owner of the seed and others have said that the husk will also be distributed amongst them like the grain although the husk has not been mentioned. If the condition is that the husk shall belong to the owner of the seed, the *muzariah* will be valid. If the condition is that the husk will not belong to the owner of the seed and will belong to his partner, this *muzariah* will be invalid. If the owner of the land desires to take the standing crop this is permissible. In this case the owner of the land will be asked to cut down the crops as stipulated according to his share, and share it with the lessee or hand over the share of the lessee or bear the burden of looking after the crops till they ripen. Whatever had been agreed upon may then be realised from the yield of the crops.

Musaqat ⁴³:

Musaqat in trees is like *muzariah* in land and *musaqat* is known as "mu'amlah". The specification of the period is essential in case of *musaqat*. If the period is not mentioned, (*musaqat*) is chargeable on the first fruit. If a period has been specified during which the fruits may ripen or they may not ripen, *musaqat* is permissible because in this case the failure of the purpose, which *prima facie* is partnership in produce, is not certain.

It is not permissible for the owner of the trees to eject the *amil* ⁴⁵ without reason and similarly it is not permitted to the *amil* to abandon his work without reason. (This is) contrary to the case of *muzariah* wherein the owner of the land, who is the owner of the seed too, can terminate *muzariah*. If the stipulated period for *musaqat* comes to an end and the fruits are still on (the trees) and have not ripened, it is the duty of the *amil* to look after the trees till the fruits ripen and he is not entitled to any wages. He is responsible for all the labour. This is contrary to the case of *muzariah* for in that case the payment of wages to the labourer becomes incumbent, as he has the status of an *ajir* after the expiry of the period of *musaqat* and he (alone) is not responsible for the entire labour involved, but both are responsible.

The *musaqat* is terminated for several reasons. One of the reasons is where the *amil* is found to be a thief, and there is the danger that he will steal leaves of trees and raw fruits. Secondly, the *amil* falls ill and is incapable of work. If the person hands over bare land to an *amil* on the condition that he will plant trees within three years so that he has a share in land and trees to the extent of half, such a contract is not valid. The owner of land will be entitled to the entire yield of fruits and the *amil* will be paid wages proportionate to his labour.

CHAPTER III

ON KNOWING THE PARTICULARS OF JARA'ID (REGISTERS)

Jarida etymologically means the bark of date-palm and that bark which is taken off from a branch or that which has been separated from one. Its plural is *jara'id*. When a person strips himself of clothes he is said to be *mujarrad*. It is recorded in *Kanz-ul-Hisab* of Abul Qasim Mustaufi that *jarida* is a register which has no binding. Etymologically *jarida* is the branch of date-palm and it is so called because it has been separated from the tree and its plural is *jara'id*. A person is said to have become *mujarrad* when he takes off his clothes. *Jarida* is also used for a group of soldiers detached from the army for some duty. Some scribes have said that *jarida* is (the name) of a white paper which is folded and creased, so that entries may be made thereon. It is called *jarida* because it has been set apart for keeping accounts. It is recorded in *Muntakhab-ul-Hisab*: "The folded paper is called *jarida*—that on which accounts are written, and it is called *jarida* because it has been separated for keeping accounts."

Be it known, that the first register which is required by a *muharrir* clerk) is *Daftar-e-Roznama* (Day Book). It is known as "*Ummul Jara'id*", or *Jaridat-ut Ta'liq* (the source of all registers) for whatever happens during the day is recorded therein, such as deposits, receipts, salaries, *khil'ats*, leases, charities, contracts, and transfer of a village from one to another, deeds taken from contractors, and lessors, vouchers and details of disbursements, and details of pensions, payments, assignations, rewards, legal dues, contract deeds, formal recommendations and *parwanajat*, official letters that are received and those that are sent out. In short, whatever takes place that day or any other happening should be recorded (therein).

Briefly the basis of the art of *istifa* consists in the knowledge of figures, and the entire art of this branch of knowledge is contained in the pearl scattering words of Amirul Mominin 'Ali (may God be pleased with him!) who was the *Mustaufi* of the Prophet. "*Al-hashv* is the account written under different heads; *bariz* is (technically written) outside the *hashv*; to every detailed statement there is a short summary, and for every summary there is a detailed statement; and the totals of the two must tally; if you have to pay, make the entry first and then pay; if you have to receive (anything) receive first and then make an entry." From these few words can be learnt the entire knowledge of this art. As the knowledge of figures of accounts is the essence of this science, therefore, they (the scribes) begin it with an account of book-keeping.

Be it known that whatever the scribes of Khorasan, Iraq, Ghazni and Fars have written about it, has been followed in practice for years and what the learned men of Ghazni have approved and adopted has been followed here. And upto this day this system has obtained amongst the scribes.

After the praise of God, the name of the month should be written across the length of '*umm-ul-hisab*, and the date and the year under the *hashv*

of that month, and the day should be written in smaller letters, and entries about income and expenditure which have to be made from the top of the paper across the length of *sadr-ul-hisab*; the clerk should carefully mention the name of the payer, and the *amil*, the date of the (final) receipt so that no doubt should arise at the time of posting. If the receipt is returned and has to be made out in the name of some one else, it should be written in the *roznama*, at the very place where the correction is made, and the line drawn under the name of the payer and the *amil*. These entries should be made out in the name of the second payer or *amil*, and he should write the date of issuing of the second receipt. And if in the place where the receipt has been entered some discrepancy occurs, the reason for it and the actual (amount) which has been paid in the name of the payer should be written clearly over the sum in slanting letters. And whatever has been agreed upon should be written clearly under it. On the following day the name of the day should be written (afresh) as explained above. Whatever has happened that day should be written upto the end of that month. After that the name of the second month should be written opposite the first month and the days should be recorded according to the same system as stated above. If deeds of assignation are entered, true copy of the deed of assignation, word by word within a quarter of the page from the right hand should be written in straight lines. When the scribe comes to the sum total of the *qabala-e-mashruh* the same should be written in *bariz*, and if there are further details, he should ascertain them. After that *qabala-e-mashruh* should be written on three quarters of the page from the right side. If in the *khatut* a sum is mentioned, it should be written in a line and (the scribe) should not write it in *bariz*. The Day Book is the chief source for the recording of transactions so that one may refer to the Day Book for all previous transactions.

Daftar-ul-Awarij: It has been said in the *Muntakhab-ul-Hisab*: "*Awarij* is the Arabicized form of *awarah* (a wanderer) and the meaning of the word in the Persian language is that it is "what is transferred and recorded", for that which is in the mind or on the tongue is transferred to it and that which is paid in several instalments is recorded in it, till whatever is due is fully paid up."

It is further written in that book: "*Awarij* are columns of accounts" and *awarijah* are those (items) which a clerk records at the time of entering the various official transactions. He writes the name of the remitter across the length of *sadr-al-hisab* and records the various payments made by him in brief and without explanations or details. He then writes below it in the column of the *'umm-al-hisab*, the payments made out of it. Here he records the heads of every receipt and payment made by the remitter and writes those receipts in proper order.

The use of this register is that whenever the Day Book is to be consulted, it is to be referred to from the date of this very register and that the entire disbursements can be seen here at a glance. It is the duty of the clerk that

he should compare the Day Book with the *awarijah* so that nothing is left out, which might cause him anxiety. If there is a salaried person, receipt (of the salary received) by him should be taken from him.

Daftar-ul Mufridat : The *mufridat* is a register in which the accounts and transactions of a (particular) year are recorded. Every *shiq* and *iqta'* should be written separately in the column of *sadr-ul-hisab* and the details about them should be written under a line, sufficiently long, under which this statement could be completely written. This statement is called the "statement under the main *hashv.*" It is never without four particulars, all of which are called *arkan-e-sadar* or the components of the *sadar* : firstly, the name of the remitter ; secondly, the nature of the transaction, thirdly, the entire period specified from the beginning to the end, and fourthly, the date of writing. The account should bear the date and be in detail and in agreement with the authority and the orders of the *Diwan* so that the income from a territory such as *kharaj* and other items of revenue, both the normal and the extra ones, should be recorded at great length, and in detail, in keeping with the rules and customs, and should be checked, and the fact of checking noted on the *bariz* and the sign is put on all such orders. If at the time of making the entries the sign has already been drawn, it should be changed into

The leading scribes of Khorasan, Iran and Fars used to draw as the mark of inspection and comparison which occurs at the end of the entries, an oblique line in this manner If it is compared a second time, a second line is added to it and it is known as the mark of double inspection. When compared thrice a point is added over these lines and it becomes like this and this is called the comparison sign where accounts have been compared three times. If compared for the fourth time, these points are changed into and it becomes like this If it is compared for the fifth time a is added to it and it becomes like this If it is compared for the sixth time, a point is placed over it like this If it is compared for the seventh time, the point is changed into a *jazm.*

Whatever is transferred from the Day Book to the Registers of cash or stipends or others, should be marked at the top with the sign When (a writer) intends to make entries about the accounts of a remitter, he should take great care in making (credit) entries, and should ascertain the amounts to be paid by him and should pay heed to the entries about receipts and payments. He should similarly look carefully into the execution of the orders and regulations and should see that the disbursement is equal to the total (income) and that the dates and the names are above doubt. He should regard the writing in the hand of some one else as a source of (committing) mistake and (facilitating) misappropriations.

When the vouchers are verified, he should put them in order and should, then, enter them in the register. He should record before all other heads the sums carried over (the cash) and should end the writing with (entering) the total expenditure. When he completes the entries, he should

give dates. He should write the dates according to the order in which the accounts are recorded in case of every item in detail, and separately so that cash is to be entered under cash, goods under goods and corn under corn. He should date them and should compare these dates. He should, then, turn to totalling and should take first of all the fractions and then keep to the order of the integral numbers. He should first take the units, then the tens, then the hundreds and then the thousands. He should, then, begin the totalling of every item lengthwise from the corner of the paper and should be very careful in his totalling. He should add for the second time lengthwise from the bottom of the paper, so that if the previous total is obtained, it is correct (and above doubt). He should, then, write the *sarbala* of the headings of the accounts. For instance, he should write first the *sarbala* of the total expenditure and should follow this order till he reaches the *sarbala* of the cash in hand. He should record down every *sarbala* that he arrives at. He should find out the balance with care and should take the signature of the remitter over it. If there is no balance, he should write at the end of the account "the account is closed" equal in length to the line to be drawn for recording the balance. If under the head of expenses all (amounts) are spent, he should write: "The total amount is exhausted." If the writer has recorded a balance for the first year in the account (of the remitter) and then another sum falls due (in his name) out of the balance for the last year, it should be recorded with words: *Jama' Zaleka* (add to it). If after adding and totalling up all the sums, something more is to be added to it again, it is better that he should record it with the word and add that amount to this. In all matters of accounts he should observe the directions of *Diwan-i-Ishraf* supported by the seal (signatures) of the *Diwan*.

There is difference of opinion about the method of work. The eminent scribes of Khorasan record the sums received in *bariz* and what is to be recorded in *bariz*, they write it in the *hashv* and they enter the income like the expenditure. The learned writers of Sistan, Ghazni and Iraq write the sums received in the *hashv* and say that that which is due should be entered in *bariz*. In these days this is the accepted practice of the eminent writers here. A writer may write whatever he has to pay in the *amal* and he should write in the *hashv* whatever he intends to receive back. After these entries he should write the *qarar* and should enter in the *qarar* the balance after subtracting *bariz-i-amal* from *bariz-i-jumlatan* in the *bariz qarar*. When the *bariz qarar* is written, he should subtract the *bariz-i-kharch* from the *bariz qarar*. If there is a balance he should record the balance. If he mentions something else and records the balance under it, he should enter the date and also the detailed account against the date when he entered the balance.

When, at the time of preparation of accounts, the entire balance is realised from the remitter or the *amil*, the writer should record it and should prepare a detailed and itemwise account sheet, according to the registers and hand it over to (the *amil*), so that it might be of use to him later, as an

evidence. If he does not hand over the detailed account sheet to him, he should enter the receipt with the signs of settlement of accounts and should return it to him. If any amount is found later to be due from the remitter, or if anything is recorded wrongly in his name and an increase or a decrease is caused thereby, he should inform him of it and should not be annoyed if any further inquiries are made. He should rather be afraid of the reckoning on the Day of Judgment and should not raise unreasonable objections in (matters of) account, for "whosoever disputes an account will be punished (on the Day of Judgment)."

Daftar Jami'ul Hisab :—It is a register wherein the accounts of a *wilayat*, a *shiq*, an *iqtah'* or the lands of a grantee or farmer of revenue are recorded and entered itemwise, so that if ever the king wants to know as to what are the revenues and the proceeds from various items of income, what is the expenditure for the current year and what are the arrears and in whose name they are, such a register is required to be prepared and that is called *jami'-ul-hisab*. As is written in detail and at greater length in the register of *mufridat* of statement about fields or divisions, the writer should enter income under income, expenditure under expenditure, and should record various items in the name of each person so that cash is entered under cash, salaries under salaries, stipends under stipends. He should add together all the expenses and other items of expenditure and strike the balance; and he should take great care in recording the items of expenditure. After checking the income and expenditure he should find out the balance, as to the amount (due), if any, and under what head and against whose name, so that the *jami'-ul-hisab* may be prepared.

In these days, this register has gone out of use. Nobody knows how to prepare it and (the writers) are content with preparing only summaries.

The register of salaries, of awards, of title deeds, of contracts, of permits and orders, and the like, the register of accounts of *karkhanas* and of buildings and the register of divisions (of crops) or division of booty, (description) of every cultivator, of the kinds of crop (sown), the *kharaj* due from every person and (taxes for) grazing animals are all recorded (therein) in detail. Registers relating to principal taxes and the additional taxes, and such registers as are kept in every village and town, should be kept by the scribes. There should be a copy of these registers in the *Diwan* as well. The various accounts should be revised. In case of doubt as to the principal or the additional income of a village this very register is to be consulted and details studied so that all doubts are removed.

CHAPTER IV

A DESCRIPTION OF THE QUALIFICATIONS OF VARIOUS OFFICERS OF DIWAN (THE REVENUE DEPARTMENT) AND OTHER THINGS CONCERNING THEM⁴⁴

SECTION I

THE WAZIR

(The word) *wazir* is derived from (the root) '*wazr*'. Etymologically '*wazr*' means 'a lofty mountain' to which people resort for protection. A minister is called a *wazir*, because the people take refuge with him, for instance (the author of) *Umdat-ul-Hisab* writes : "(The word) *wazir* is derived from the (root) *wazr* and it is a mountain where people take shelter and seek refuge, and he is called a *wazir* because people seek his protection in their affairs."

Others have stated that (the word) *wazir* is derived from (the root) *wizr* and etymologically *wizr* means 'to bear the burden of sins.' For instance, God says : "And nobody bears the burden of another." (The word) *wazir* has the form of '*fa'yeel*', in the sense of one who does something, and *wazir* therefore means one who bears the burden and this is the sense in which the word *wazir* is generally used, for he bears the heavy burden of the kingdom on behalf of the king and that is why he is called a *wazir*, and in some books it is stated that the *wazir* is *dastur*.

Firstly, a *wazir* should be from amongst those closely related to the king, in accordance with the commandment of God, "And appoint for me a minister from my own family, my own brother, Haroon, with whom I might strengthen my back and whom I might make my partner in my work."

God Almighty has revealed that Moses, the Prophet (peace be on him!) made a request to God thus : "Appoint for me a minister who must be from amongst my own (people), who might strengthen my back and make him (O God) my partner in my work, so that he might help me in my work and let him be my brother."

And the Prophet of God (peace be on him!) says : "I have two ministers in the heavens and two ministers on this earth ; in the heavens they are (the angels) Gabriel and Michael and on the earth they are Abu Bakr and 'Umar (may God be pleased with them!)"'. This holy verse and this holy tradition both prove that a minister should be related to the king as a relative (*tabiat*) and (the word) *taba* means a son, a brother, a friend or a near relation. The office of a minister is the highest office and it should not be entrusted to any one outside this group for the affairs of a kingdom cannot be set right without a minister. The order of a *Wazir* is like the order of the king. Therefore, the relation of a minister to the king should be that of a *tabiat*, that is, a son or a brother. If the sons, brothers and relatives are passed over and this office is conferred upon some one else, he must be a person who had been professing loyalty and praying for the prosperity of the king, even before the beginning of his suzerainty. For

instance, the *Majlis-e Ali*, the master of the kingdoms of truth and sincerity, the chief of the *maliks* of the east and of the *wazirs*, Ulugh Qutlugh Azam Humayun, Khan-e-Jehan, who is one like Asaf, (the *wazir*) of Solomon, with the dignity of Buzurjemehr, just like Nausherwan, the favourite of Muhammad Tughlaq, who like Ayaz of Mahmud, has been favoured in the court of the kings of excellent qualities for his faithfulness and loyalty and who has been distinguished amongst the kings for his generosity and kindness, who has been, as a result of former services, dignified by the Khalifa, the Alexander of the day (may God perpetuate his Khilafat!) with the office of *wizarat* and this office has been distinguished by his person, who is endowed with admirable qualities. He is held in favour for his excellent and praiseworthy traits of character, is famed for being a loyal servant of the king and has far excelled his contemporaries and peers and has proved himself worthy of the office of *wizarat* with respect to every affair of the kingdom. May God Almighty decorate the sleeves of the robe of the kingdom of this king with the embroidery of continuity till the Day of Judgment.

Secondly, a *wazir* should be well versed in science, philosophy and traditions, should be of a generous nature, large hearted, cultured and kind, of pearl like purity and of pure beliefs, of good behaviour, wise, of sound opinions, of great sagacity and industry, of great insight, courageous, a leader of armies, hospitable, sweet tongued, pious, and a lover of piety and an enemy of vices, a fine calligraphist, well versed in account keeping, of open disposition, benevolent, quick witted, patient and cheerful, truthful and regular in offering prayers, God-fearing, compassionate, very generous, true to his word, moderate in his punishments and quick in (rewarding), free from malice or pride, free from tyranny or jealousy and abstaining from oppression and cruelty.

When the office of a *wazir* is adorned by such a person, no disorders occur in any way in the kingdom. The affairs of the state are well organised and the king can with peace of mind indulge in pleasure or in war. The instruments of the administration of the affairs of the kingdom are the ministers. There have been in this world many rulers from amongst women or minors who were unfit to do anything (themselves), but their ministers successfully performed their duties and administered for them the important affairs of their kingdom, and their country was, as a result of the ability of their ministers saved from the evil intentions of their enemies. A wise minister becomes a just king as the sun becomes the day and the moon becomes the night. A king attains glory by virtue of a *wazir*, as God, the High and the Sublime, has revealed: "And we removed from thee thy burden which had bent thy back." Even if a king is learned, wise and mighty, he has no other alternative but to keep a sagacious and God fearing *wazir*. The prophets who were kings as well, and who always received Divine revelations, for instance Uriah for the Prophet Daud, Asif for the Prophet Solomon, Aristotle for Zulqarnain, (Alexander), the Barmecides for the (Abbaside) Caliphs, Buzurjemehr for Nausherwan—none of them was without a minister, for the kings have to lead armies (for conquests) and to

attend to affairs of peace and war, while the prosperity of the kingdom, the collection and realisation of the revenues, the appointment of the *amil*s and the accountants, inspection of the *karkhanas*, the mustering of horses, camels and other animals, the payment of salaries and remunerations to the army and the king's retinue, providing of comforts to the subjects, the posting of bodyguard, the payment of salaries and of stipends to the jurists and others, and payment of their stipends, to orphans and the widows the regulation and administration of the affairs of the learned and the philosophers and the supervision of the work of the officials and of the affairs of the various departments, all these concern the *wazirs*.

It is the duty of a *wazir* that he should begin his work every day with religious affairs and should give them precedence over the worldly affairs, so that if someone else commits a mistake, God does not take him to account for that. Whenever the cases of oppressed people reach him, the *wazir* should neither keep them pending nor should he delay (in deciding them). He should act according to the commands of the *Shari'ah* and the facts of the case. The *wazir* should, during the term of his *wizarat*, remit at the earliest opportunity, the undesirable taxes and all irregular State demands, which become burdensome to the subjects, by reason of being excessive. Otherwise he will have to bear the consequences on the Day of Judgment. He should consider himself as an intermediary and a trustee between the king and his subjects. He should exert himself in punishing the oppressors and chastising the tyrants in proportion to their crimes. If the king intends to exceed the limits prescribed by the *Shari'ah* in chastising the oppressors and the tyrants, the minister should by polite means remove the idea from the blessed mind of the king. If the king proposes to undertake some commendable religious or temporal matter, the minister should encourage him and he should arrange that it is carried out quickly. He should pay without delay or excuse the salaries and the yearly stipends granted by the king to the jurists and the holy warriors, the courtiers, and other deserving persons, so that they may pray for the king with contented hearts. The minister should attend to the affairs of the Muslims.

Whenever a *wazir* intends to appoint an officer to a *wilayat* (province) as *khatib* or *amil* he should entrust such offices only to those people who are regarded as religious minded by the subjects and who have in their hearts the fear of God, the Holy and the Sublime. He should not appoint them from amongst a body of men, who are dishonest, cruel and oppressive. He should not give access to the *diwan* to people who regard oppression and tyranny as a qualification and consider maliciousness and backbiting as a wise thing. If the blessed mind of the king puts off (his decision on) a matter and seeks the advice of the *wazir* in that matter, the latter should not give his reply in haste and he should only advise what appears to him to be beneficial, because the person whose advice is sought should be trustworthy. If the matter, upon which his advice is sought (by the king), relates to the grant of some *iqta'* to an Amir or conferment of an office on the recommendation of the *Sahib-e-Sadr* and the *wazir* and advises the king

(to the contrary) and the king has conferred that *iqtah* upon that *Amir* or that *mansab* (office) upon that nominee of the *Sahib-e-Sadr* and (later on) it is found that (the appointment) was a mistake, the *wazir* should not draw the attention of (the king) to it, nor should he make a show of his better judgment in that matter, for this would offend the king and the temper of the king would not stand it. If the king openly orders the carrying out of an unwise measure, which he regards as right, the *wazir* should, for the time being, agree to it submissively; but if the good of religion and State is not consistent with it, the *wazir* should state his (opinion) in suitable words about what is right and thus remove it from the blessed mind of the king. And if he (the king) persists (in the course), he should not give up the attempt and should continue his effort. If the *wazir* is annoyed with some one or for some reason he bears enmity towards that person, but the king is kind to him and the king regards him with honour and respect, the *wazir* should forego taking revenge and should treat such a man with consideration. He should not be afraid of the fact that that man, if he had an opportunity, might attempt to injure him, for God Almighty would not, as a reward for his having forgiven that man, give the latter the upper hand over the *wazir*.

The *wazir* should always, as far as possible, fulfil the expectations of the aged and experienced persons and the intelligent and wise young men, who are well known and eminent in the city. He should actively assist them by promises of providing them with jobs and means of livelihood and should consider it his duty to help them.

If the king, at the instigation of an enemy or as a result of the jealousy of a malicious person, turns against them and intends to do them an injury or a wrong, the *wazir* should not agree to it and he should, by some means or other, turn away the king from this intention. He should so execute the important affairs of the State that no evil is uttered against him to the king. If (may God save us from this!) the king does him an injury and intends to further injure him, the *wazir* should not take it to heart. If the king, out of consideration for his *wazir* forgives him, the *wazir* should always thank him for his bounty and should not think of the previous anger of the king, and regard him (the king) and the slanderer alike (forgiven). If consideration is shown to the courtiers of the king and his near relations, he (the *wazir*) should treat the courtiers and the ordinary people alike.

If the courtiers of the king and his near relations have a claim against a subject or some person, the *wazir* should not permit partiality or show leniency in their case, nor should he be partial to the strong. If the *wazir* fears that as a result of their relationship to the king, they would do him some injury and, therefore, he is unable to decide the matter according to the law of the *Shari'ah* and the rules applicable to the case, he should hand over the case to the king and represent to the king whatever is true and right and solicit his orders. He may thus get out of this difficulty in this suitable manner. When any of the commanders of the army and the leaders of the forces, who are kept in readiness to exterminate the enemies of the Faith and the kingdom, undertake such enterprises, the *wazir* should

enjoin upon them that they should not be proud, that (they) should rely upon the favour of God, should depend on the ever increasing glory of the king and that whenever the commanders encamp, they should keep watch over the property, the horses and the goods of the subjects and should avoid billeting troops in their houses and workshops. As a result of all this, he would be saved from natural calamities, his enemies would be vanquished and his object would be realised.

He should always follow (the example) of the *wazirs* of the past, and should strive towards self-improvement. He should avoid and shun all bad habits to which human beings are prone and should practise self-admonition day and night and should reform his conduct by pious acts. He should not feel angry with others for things which are not agreeable to him. He should speak kindly to his followers and his dependents, so that he might be loved by them and might prove himself worthy of leadership and of dignity. He should overlook the faults of his servants and should not be severe in punishing the ordinary people for every act of disobedience. He should avoid admonishing and chastising the people excessively when swayed by anger. When wrath overwhelms him, it is better for him to seek atonement (*kaffara*) so that he might be able to make amends later. He should, as far as possible, adorn himself with the ornament of forbearance, for this would prove as an investment for happiness in both the worlds. He should not take to frivolity or revelry and should prefer wakefulness to sleep and seriousness to levity. He should read very often the stories of the ministers of old, so as to gain experience. He should in most of his affairs consult and seek advice from people of honour and of experience. He should not be vain of his own opinion and his own judgment. If, God forbid, he discovers a mistake made by someone, of which the injury extends to the State revenues, he should cover it with the skirt of forgiveness and he should give him a warning and should not convey it to the ears of the king, lest a precedent may be set in this respect and his own affairs (one day) result in evil. He should make it a habit to always do good and should make it a habit to be kind and polite. He should regard it as obligatory upon him to help those in distress and should not feign indifference to such an extent as to be mistaken for ignorance. He should always feel happy at the least favour shown by the king to anyone and should regard it his greatness that his equals and contemporaries were so many, for his worthiness to the office can be recognised only by the existence of such people and his excellence can be understood only when he attains to dignity during the time of his peers.

A *wazir* should mix and keep constant company with men of learning, and wisdom. He should not speak ill of any creature though his enemies may speak ill of him ; he should not punish them, even when he has the power to do so. Their evil will revolve round them and the *wazir* should take it for certain that there is no enemy for a man more powerful than his own wickedness. Verse :

Whoever rises against you, leave him to the hands of time
For time is your servant, who will avenge you."

God Almighty says : "And wicked malice encompasses none but its own master." The best adornments of a *wazir* are modesty and truthfulness. A *wazir*, who is devoid of these, cannot establish his claims to the office of *wizarat*. A *wazir* should be fearless and truthful and should not be avaricious. The example of one who takes bribes is that of aloe wood that burns itself and spreads its odour to others. A *wazir* should collect the revenues with leniency and kindness, and he should appoint intelligent and skilful men for collecting every tax, for if delay occurs in the realisation of taxes it is never without (resultant) calamity. He should (therefore) realise the taxes with kindness and consideration and not by punishment and severity.

He should avoid invoking (by his actions) the curses of the Muslims and the *zimmis*. He should not cause injury to anybody from among the high or low without a lawful excuse, nor should he reject the just claims (of anybody). He should consider it his bounden duty to show mercy to the people in general. He should regard the prayers of the Muslims as beneficial and effective. "Escape the imprecations of the oppressed" is the saying of the Prophet. He should not feel vain on account of the kindness (shown to him) by the king or because of the great number of his relatives, or the multitude of his helpers and supporters and because of the dignity of his office, because the prosperity of this vile world is transitory. He should not, as far as possible, restrain his hands from bestowing charities and should discharge his obligations towards God. He should always patronise men of skill and learning and should not honour the low and the base born, for otherwise men of learning and of skill would turn away from him.

A *wazir* should be a man of wealth, so that he might not oppress the people for the sake of money. The *wazir* should, when the *Sadar*, the notables, and men of learning and of excellence visit him, treat them with honour. He should satisfy their demands for which they visited him and should regard their coming to his place as a matter of honour. He should be superior to his equals in efficiency and skill and should be so courageous that he should not be afraid of any of the enemies of the king. If the king deems it advisable to despatch him as an envoy to an enemy, he should be able to successfully carry out his mission. He should not, as far as possible, persuade the king to wage war. Nausherwan has recorded it in his sayings that "that *wazir* is the most despicable who leads his king to the path of war, for in every thing (else) there is some justification, or urgency, for expending money, but in warfare body and life are demanded." A *wazir* should see that there are no alliances among the *maliks* and the *amirs*, for their union with each other breeds sedition. The *wazir* should now and then honour his soldiers and retainers with kind treatment and rewards and should not decree or make large deductions from their salaries, so that they should not lose their affection for him. If a *wazir* realises from rational thinking or from reports that disobedience and disaffection would be caused by a certain person, he should immediately apply a remedy. He should not be negligent of the affairs of the enemies of the country and should keep himself well

informed about the affairs of the enemies of the kingdom. He should employ in his service, for this purpose, a number of persons intelligent and well-informed and should provide them with facilities (to collect information) and should not grudge them anything.

He should keep himself engaged in the important affairs of the kingdom. He should carefully study the past and should provide a remedy for the present and should be prepared with a remedy for the future so that in an emergency he may not be confounded and may not fail to do what is right. He should be extremely particular in enlisting soldiers and retainers and in manufacturing arms. He should collect taxes and wealth according to the law (of *Shari'ah*) and custom and should not permit that which is forbidden by the law of *Shari'ah* and custom. He should enjoin upon the *amils* and revenue agents not to practise tyranny so that the subjects may prosper. He should abolish oppressive taxes, for when the people are reduced to poverty the taxes are not realised and when the taxes are not realised, the army cannot be maintained.

In short there is no work beset with greater dangers than the office of a *wazir*, for all the ill and diseased people of the realm of the king get their remedy from him and no other person has so many enemies as a *wazir* has. May God the Almighty keep all the just *wazirs* under his own protection.

SECTION II

THE MUSHRIF

(The word) *Mushrif* is derived from *ishraf* and etymologically its meaning is "to see", that is, to be well informed. In some books its meaning is "to be able to see". In some dictionaries *ishraf* is "to look down from above". It has been seen in *Umda*, "There is an additional beauty in the word *mushrif* and it is for this very reason that he is called *mushrif* and not *mullah*, for *sharaf* is elevation and as the *mushrif* is highly stationed, he is therefore called *mushrif* and not *mullah* (or well informed)".

A *mushrif* should be one of the notables of the court, whose ancestors have had position and status in the country. He should be a man of learning, of honesty, of integrity, of piety, of excellent character, efficient, great in kindness, one who abstains from what is forbidden and (avoids) frivolousness and levity, is forbearing, generous, successful and one whose tongue is free from shameful and base things and whose heart is free from vanity and pride. He is neither very exacting in matters of accounts, nor indifferent to them. Anger does not dominate his temperament, nor malice his heart, when he is appointed to the office of the *mushrif*, he is expected to follow the path of *Shari'ah* and accepted practices and to regard what is opposed to the *Shari'ah* and custom as sheer oppression. Be it known that *ishraf* is of two kinds: the first is the *ishraf* of a *wilayat* and the other is that of factories (*karkhanas*).

Now the first kind of *ishraf* is the one in a *wilayat* : he (the *Mushrif*)

is (mostly concerned with) the collection of taxes. The *mushrif* should know fully about the taxes sanctioned by the *shari'ah* and custom and that there are certain taxes established by the *shari'ah* and certain others, which were introduced in the days of the past kings. The *mushrif* should know that the taxes sanctioned by the *Shari'ah* are of twelve types, as has (already) been discussed in the chapter dealing with the heads of public revenue. He should collect them according to the *shari'ah* and custom. It is obligatory upon a *mushrif* that he should practise great caution in collecting these taxes. He should put into writing the entire collection and every realisation and should record them in detail at great length, under various heads. The entries cannot but fall under one of (the following) three categories : (i) *Irtifah* (ii) *Iftitah* and (iii) *Istikhraj*.

Irtifah is the receipt of corn and other kinds of produce from the land, and taxes levied from the artisans and workmen. The *mushrif* should know that these are the sources of revenue and he should prepare the account according to the lunar year. The difference between a solar year and a lunar year is equal to eleven days less a few seconds and for thirty solar years there are thirty one lunar years and within this period thirty two *kharif* crops are gathered. How can the *mushrif* know as to when (they) fall due, if he does not know fully the method of converting the lunar year into solar year? The leaders of the army should be paid their salaries from the treasury and in this respect the *mushrif* should exert himself to his utmost. He should fully understand the method of converting the lunar year into solar year. He should not permit anything, even a *dirham* or a *dam*, to be spent or wasted on account of his ignorance. He should not, out of malice or enmity, demand from any person that which is not legally due (from him), for he would be held responsible for it before God and on the Day of Judgment his enemy would demand retribution. The kings and others have always relied upon the spoken words of the *mushrif*.

SECTION III

THE MUSTAUFU AND MATTERS RELATING TO HIM

(The word) *mustaufi* is derived from *istifa* and etymologically it means the full realisation of the dues from others, and a *mustaufi* is a collector of the dues of the *bait-ul-mal* from the *amils* and the *vakils* etc., that is why he is called *mustaufi*. A *mustaufi* should belong to the family of notables and leading men of the court and he should be well known for his integrity and probity and his honesty, reputed for his rectitude and known for his fidelity. He should know enough of *shari'ah* so as to be able to maintain the registers in Arabic characters. He should make entries in the *Jama'* with the concurrence of the payer, and of (the expenditure) with fairness and with proper authority of the *amil* and by mutual agreement and after confirmation should arrive at the balances carefully and patiently. He should not be ignorant of the science of jurisprudence and should be able to administer

justice, after hearing the (different) claims according to the law of *shari'ah*. Nothing which is opposed to the *shari'ah* should pass his tongue and his pen, as is recorded in the *Kanz-ul Hisab* : "A *Mustaufi* should have good knowledge of the *shari'ah* and an understanding of the pure accounts ; he should be an expert in the signs and (the system) of figures used in the office of the Diwan. He should utter nothing but truth and should not audit the accounts but with honesty. He should pay equal attention to the (interest) of the State as well as the *ajir*, for the Prophet has said : "Whoever is nominated between two persons, should be considerate in his words and looks (and act) in the interest of both the parties. He should not raise his voice (in anger) against one of them, unless he raises it against the other as well."

He should make fear of God his habit and practice in all circumstances. He should avoid all sorts of jokes and frivolous talk and should avoid haste or heat. He should make uprightness and dignity his practice. He should not lose his temper. If some one (says to him) something that is not to his liking, he should not enter into argument with him and should ignore the same. He should not be jealous or malicious or self-opinionated and should be kind to all and should treat the public at large with politeness. He should give up enmity and all old feuds (against others). If somebody had intended or intends to (harm him), he should not strive to take revenge. He should, as far as possible, return good for evil. He should not oppress the payer of revenue or the *amil*, nor should he allow oppression of the people nor dispute the accounts (unnecessarily) "He should not be too contentious about accounts nor should he refuse to accept an explanation. Auditing means that you should explain the work of an *amil* to him". It is the duty of *mustaufi* to make things clear to the *amil* and carry out his work efficiently. He should not extort money nor should he take bribes, nor should he demand the *amil's* perquisites. Bribe is what a writer demands for the work which is a part of his duties. God Almighty has revealed : "And for them (*Amils* of these taxes) bribe is that which a man exacts for serving the need of one in distress and to protect him from what is undesirable". This is because man is ordained to help the oppressed and the afflicted and because the Prophet has said : "A man will be questioned for his overt acts as well as for his hidden acts."

He should not delay the business of the people of God for the sake of his own work and interest. Whatever he says or does, should not be far from truth. He should give a satisfactory and true answer to whatever is enquired from him, so that contradiction does not occur in his words and deeds. The *mustaufi* is an officer of the *diwan* and contradictory orders and inconsistencies in his words are not desirable. He should not permit injury or harm to be done to an *amil* or to a tax payer on his account for he would be held responsible for it on the Day of Judgment and (it would) result in his infamy in this world and his embarrassment in the next. He should avoid the following while discharging his duties: to take over the work of an *amil* and entrusting it to another person to serve his own ends and not in

order to increase the income of the *Diwan* ; to spend the revenues by subterfuges and to divert it to his own use and to make it over to his own dependents ; to keep the vouchers and the registers in his own house ; to stand surety for others ; to accept security of a person or property ; to advance loans to others or to take loans from others ; to mix with them or to keep company with them too frequently ; to invite them to his house as guests and to visit their houses on some pretext ; to demand necessities for his household, such as grass or fuel, from them, or to accept presents from them, as is written in the *Kanz-ul Hisab*, "He should not offer himself for presents, for it has been related from 'Umar (may God be pleased with him!) that, when he asked the Prophet about presents, the latter replied : "There is no harm if it has not been anticipated and expected'." As has already been related, the temperament of a *mustaufi* should be according to the four elements, that is he should be, in the first instance, pure like the fire, secondly, gentle like the air, thirdly, soft like the water and fourthly, trustworthy like the earth.

The *mustaufi* should so arrange his method of work that nobody gets to know about it, nor has anybody any objection against it, and no one gets any information about his accounts. If he has doubts about the applicability of any law to a problem, he should consult the jurists and the learned about it and should not feel ashamed of it, the verification of the rules of the *Shari'ah* about these practices to the advantage of these two *diwans*, the *Diwan-i-Shara'* and the *Diwan-i-Mu'amlat*, for *mu'amlat* is based upon honesty and (observance of the rules of) *shari'ah*. He should not take any action without the consent of the *wazir*. He should prepare the (State) demands beforehand, but should not make entries of demands before they fall due and his disbursements should not be without orders. If a certain expenditure is clear to him, but its voucher is not there, he should enter it under the sign (.....) and should not postpone it till the voucher is obtained. And if after the balance has been struck, the voucher is produced, he should write under it that the voucher has been seen and entries made accordingly. He should carry forward whatever excess there is on the income side (credit) or the expenditure side (debit); and when he completes the accounts and carries forward the dues and finds out the balance, he should take the signature of the payer below the balance, so that he should escape blame. He should endeavour, as far as possible, to preserve and protect the registers, should enjoin the same upon his subordinates and should (carefully) preserve the vouchers. He should not show his registers or his writing to any person. That he should not find himself in difficulty at the time of need, he should not be lazy in writing, nor postpone the postings of one day to the next day, nor should he rely upon his memory. He should re-audit every account which has been closed. He should practise great caution and should keep them (registers) in the office. The entire art of the *istifa* has been described in the pearl scattering words of the Commander of the Faithful, Hazrat 'Ali, who was the *mustaufi* of the Prophet : "*Hashv* is the account written under different heads ; the *bariz*

(technically written) outside the *hashw* ; to every detailed statement there is a short summary, and for every summary there is a detailed statement ; and the total must tally ; if you have to pay, make the entry first and then pay ; if you have to receive anything, receive first and then make an entry.”

From these few words the entire knowledge of this art can be gathered.

SECTION IV

OF THE NAZIR AND THE WORK APPERTAINING TO HIS OFFICE

(The word) *nazir* is derived from (the root) *nazr*, and etymologically the meaning of (the word) *nazr* is to see or to cast a glance, *i. e.*, the *nazir* inspects the business of the office of the *diwan*. A *Nazir* should be one of the notables of the court. He should be of noble birth, sagacious, exceedingly learned and perfect in wisdom. He should be able to comprehend, through his insight, from the words and actions of persons, as to what is their real intention. The *Diwan Nazir* was established in Khorasan and before that it did not exist in the time of the kings of Iran and their successors. And the dignity of the office of a *Nazarat*, as some of the efficient men have said, has precedence over the office of a *barid*. In the reign of the martyred Sultan Ghiyas-ud-din (may God illumine his journey to the next world!) Sharaful Mulk, son of Khwaja Sadrul Mulk Najm-ud-din, the *wazir* and the *qazi* of the days of Nasir-ud-din was the holder of the office of the *Diwan-i-barid* and Majd-ul Mulk Majd-ud-din Hanafi was the holder of the office of the *Diwan-i-Nazr*; and in the sublime court he took his seat below the *barid*. This is a proof that the office of a *Nazir* has been deemed higher than the office of a *barid*? And the *nazir*, in a sense, has been regarded as a *mushrif*. A *mushrif* is one who keeps himself informed of all affairs of a *nazir*, important or unimportant, while the duty of a *nazir* is to keep a watch over the affairs of the *mushrif*, so that whatever is done by a *mushrif*, the *nazir*; would reveal the right or wrong of it. If anything contrary to truth passes the tongue or the pen of the *mushrif*, the *nazir* should object to it. He should keep himself engaged in looking into the work of the *mushrif*, just as the *mushrif* should look into the work of the *nazir*. The words and the writings of a *nazir* have always been relied upon. The *nazir* has to record an increase in the proceeds of the *diwan* and to find out the cause of the increase. The *nazir* has to act accordingly and the blame is to be ascribed to the *mushrif*. If the *mushrif* has left out the *tawfir* to serve his own interest, then the pen of the *nazir* has to inspect it in the capacity of a *mushrif* and the *mushrif* is to blame for it. Afterwards, his words cannot be relied upon. If the *mushrif* has overlooked a particular transaction the *nazir* should act according to the advice of the *wazir* of the *diwan*.

SECTION V

THE BARID⁴⁵

Etymologically, *barid* means a messenger. In some books it is written : "*Barid* is one who is to proceed swiftly to a place, at a distance of four *farsangs*." In some lexicons the following occurs : "*Barid* is a Persian word which has been arabicised. The word is derived from the phrase "*burida*", one with the tail cut off, for the custom (prevalent) in those days was to send a horseman to bring news speedily, and the horse that was used to be more swift footed than the others, that horse's tail was cut off, so that a short tail was regarded as a sign of swift footedness. When the word was arabicised the word 'tail' was dropped and in its shortened form it became *barid*. That is why horses despatched on account of swift footedness to any place are also called *barid*." Still others have said : "Etymologically, *barid* is one who is despatched towards the king to inform him of the state of affairs". In short, *barid* is one who carries news and that which appertains to it.

The *barid* should be a man of noble birth and of noble descent and should be adorned with the ornaments of piety and integrity. He should be well versed in the science of jurisprudence, should be eloquent, a good calligraphist and (master) of an elegant style. He should be a man of few words, truthful and virtuous and should equally be a man of means. He should have a register with columns for visitors and reporters (coming to him). When a reporter comes to him, he should enter into the register the date of his arrival and the name of the reporter. He should record the report verbatim in the words of the reporters and whatever they do and report to him. And he (the *barid*) should not write it in his own words, so that if he reports from it, he should report exactly in the words of the informers.

He should always be present in the *Diwan-i-Shari'ah* and the Court of Justice, for whatever happens in these Diwans should be with his knowledge. He should keep an eye on the life and honour of the Muslims in the *Diwan-i-Shari'ah* and when he is ordered to do so, he should investigate cases. He should appear in the *Diwan-i-Maumla* and find out whether the income of the *bait-ul-mal* is administered according to the laws of the *Shari'ah*. He should strive to redress wrongs, so that if ever a *qazi* or a *wazir*, out of favouritism or leniency (towards somebody), issues orders in contravention of the *Shari'ah* or justice, he should set himself to redress it then and there, so that it is investigated and set right.

He should always be engaged in finding out the state of affairs of the kingdom and religion and whenever he receives reports about anything that is against the wishes of the king, he should inform him at once and get his (King's) orders, so that the ill-wishers of the kingdom and religion do not entertain sedition in their minds. He should make a report of the condition of people who have suffered a wrong, the moment he gets this information so that he may be rewarded for it. The stipends of the poor should be

paid, and (the condition) of the helpless, the indigent, and those in prisons for the sake of the Faith and imprisoned there for a long time, (or) if the salaries of the soldiers and the stipends of the religious people remain unpaid for a considerable time, and the king does not attend to them and thus the gates of poverty are opened on the people—the *barid* should not regard such things as unimportant matters, but should immediately draw the king's attention to them. The *barid* should be well informed about the group of people who live in retirement and whom the people esteem. He should engage himself in his work with diligence. He should live among the people of God peacefully. He should have a smiling face and a cheerful countenance, so that people do not avoid him. He should find pleasure in the company of high and low. He should be familiar with the notables and the exalted personages and the well known men, and middle class people in the city and should understand their minds so that if ever a spy reports anything about them, he may be able to judge by his knowledge and intelligence as to whether the report was true about that person or not. He should practise great caution in this respect and should report to the king only after full investigation, so that it should not bring him shame.

The *Kuttab* (news-writers) should be men of noble birth and of pure descent. A news writer should be free from vices, should not mix with people much and should keep to his own work. He should preserve his tongue from frivolity and should not say anything before it (a happening) is reported to the king, as it may result in disturbance. The sort of men who should be appointed to this duty in respect of *maliks*, the *amirs*, the *sadars* and the *wazirs* should be from among respectable men and should be from amongst those who freely move amongst the *maliks* and the *amirs*. The type of people who by nature mix freely with these people and who attend upon the *maliks* and *amirs* and their sorts should be favoured with presents and rewards (so that) they might inform him, at once, of whatever passes amongst the *maliks* and the *amirs* without any alteration. If men of integrity and intelligence are appointed to this job, they will be able to judge by their intelligence (the inter-relations of the *amirs*) from their words and acts for none else but they can bring out the secrets of the *maliks*, the *amirs*, the *sadars* and the *wazirs* from their hearts. This group of men should be distinguished, day by day, with the bounty and the generosity of the king so that their nature does not revolt against this work.

And for the thoroughfares, the markets and the public in general, such men of wisdom and truthfulness should be appointed as belong to the lowest class of people, for such people never suppress anything against others. They attend to their work regularly and perform their duties as long as they can without greed.

And to obtain information from inside the houses of the *maliks*, the *amirs* and the *sadars*, such women who are either trusted servants or serving maids or dealers in perfumes should be hired or suborned and in such a way that even the officers of the office of the *barid* should know nothing of their affairs. These women should report to the government

reporters who should (in their turn) send their reports to the *barid*. Nobody should know (the identity of) the reporter, for when a reporter is known to two persons he would (soon) be known to the entire public. If the reporter belongs to the lowest class of the people, he should make himself feared so that the people are afraid of him and serve him and he becomes well known for it (his severity). A reporter should be of such a type that he is in no way suspected of being a reporter. They should conduct themselves in such a manner that the public trusts and relies upon their word and writing, so that the end is gained. But the reporter should not cause distress to the public. In this country there are few such reporters. To maintain the dignity of the *diwan-i-barid* there should be only a few reporters and they should devote themselves entirely to their work. When this fact is known to the public, the people will say all sorts of things without any apprehension and this would serve many ends. But if there is a large number of reporters, the public comes to know of them and they keep their tongues under control and they do not say or do anything which might bring them blame and they resort to secret machinations and plots for the accomplishment of whatever is opposed to (the interest of) the country and the Faith, so that their secret is not revealed and nobody gets any information about that.

In short, the *Barid* should be honest, trustworthy, and wise, one who is able to understand by his intelligence and intuition the motive and purpose of whatever may be done by any person. His subordinates should be of a similar disposition and nature. When there is a *barid* of this type, the king can, with a contented heart, engage himself in the administration of the kingdom and in conquering new lands.

SECTION VI

OF THE WAQUF

Etymologically, (the word) *waquf* means "to stand up", "to know and to be informed", *i. e.*, the man in charge of this office has *waquf* (information) about the administration of the affairs of the *diwan*. The holder of the *diwan-i-waquf* should be one of the leading men of the court and the city and should be pious, wise and sagacious. This *diwan* was created in the capital city of Delhi (may God protect it from calamities!). It has been reported that after the death of the pious king Sultan Shams-ud-dunya-wad-din Iltutmish, his sons were minors and when they sat upon the throne of the kingdom a *malik naib* was appointed for the administration of the affairs of the kingdom and when Malik Qutbuddin Hasan Ghori was appointed as *naib* he made a request to the king that a clerk should be appointed for him in the *Diwan-i-Ali-i-Wazarat*, who should report to him about the *diwan*. This writer was known as the officer in charge of the *Aiwan-e-Niabat*. This continued for a long time and during the reign of Nasiruddin, Sultan Ghiyas-ud-din Balban was appointed as the *naib* of

the kingdom and the title of Ulugh Khan was conferred upon him. Khwaja Iftikharul Mulk Sharafuddin Muhammad Rashidi, the holder of the *Diwan-i-Arzi Mamalik* was appointed in the office of the *Diwan-i-Naib*, on the recommendation of Ulugh Khan himself. A few years passed in this way and when the throne was occupied by Sultan Ghiyasuddin Balban, he did not confer the (dignity) of the *Niabat* of the kingdom upon anybody and intended to dissolve this *diwan*. Whereupon Khwaja Iftikhar-ul Mulk Sharafuddaula wad-din Muhammad Rashidi, who was then the holder of this office, was appointed as the *Diwan-i-wazarat*. He represented thus: "The larger the number of officers of the *Diwan-i-A'la* the greater the majesty of the king. Many years have passed that this *diwan* (*Diwan-i-Niabat*) has existed in the mighty capital city of Delhi and its dissolution is far from wisdom. As the *naib* of the kingdom appoints a writer, so as to get information about the *diwan*, this officer should be designated as the *waquf*, and his status and his reports should have the position of (those of) a *naib*." Accordingly, Sultan Ghiyasuddin Balban issued orders that this *diwan* should be continued and thus it has remained in existence upto this day. As regards the status and dignity of the office, the holder of office of the *waquf* is the lowest of all other officers and upto this time no one (holding the office of *waquf* has ever issued an order in his own hand in the *Diwan-i-A'la* in the presence of the *nazir*.

This is a description of the holders of various offices in the *Wizarat-i-Diwan-i-A'la* (may it remain ever sublime!), which have been discussed in detail.

NOTES

1. *Bait-ul-Mal* : Literally, State-treasury. The term was applied to the actual building in which the financial business of the State was transacted, and, in a figurative sense, to the national exchequer. Etymologically it means the entire State revenue over which the Muslim community as a whole has claims (*Kashf-ul-Lughat*). The beginning of the institution of *Bait-ul-Mal* may be traced to the time of the Prophet, as by his time had arisen the conception of property being common to the Muslim community. The Caliph 'Umar is traditionally regarded as its official founder. It was he who first drew up *diwans*, i. e., lists of payments, and instituted a system of account keeping. See also C. H. Becker's article on *Bait-ul-Mal* in *Ency. of Islam*, Vol. I, pp. 598-99.

2. This probably refers to booty obtained during punitive expeditions within the Muslim territory or reprisals against the neighbouring States.

3. *Zavaib* : This also refers to the tax imposed on artisans and craftsmen for following a particular profession.

4. *Bagni* : An intoxicating drink prepared from hemp. Sa'ib says :

مست گفتم ز جرعه بگنی شد مزاحم ز بهنگ مستقی

5. *Zakat* : Literally the term means 'purity' or 'increase'. In Muslim Law it means a tax which is levied on definite forms of property possessed by a Muslim for a fixed period. The yield of the *Zakat* is intended only for the eight classes mentioned in Sura ix: 60. For traditions of the Prophet relating to *Zakat*, see Wensinch: *Handbook of Early Muhammadan Tradition*, pp. 264-266. See also J. Schacht's article on *Zakat* in *Ency. of Islam*, Vol. IV, pp. 1202-1205.

6. *Nisab* : the minimum of property the possession of which makes it obligatory on a person to pay *Zakat*.

7. *Amir-ul-Mominin 'Usman* : The third Caliph of Islam (644-655 A. D.). For his measures referred to here, see Aghnides : *Mohammadan Theories of Finance*, p. 296, *et seq.*

8. *Mu'az Bin Jabal* : One of the most famous companions of the Prophet. He belonged to the tribe of Khazraj and was only 20 years of age at the battle of Badr. Being well skilled in the Quran, he was left at Mecca to instruct the people in the principles of Islam. He was also sent as the head of a party of collectors of taxes to South Arabia. Later he became Qazi of Yemen. He was a leading person in the counsels of Abu Bakr and 'Umar, the latter having placed him in charge of Syria.

9. *Imam Azam Abu Hanifa* : (699-767), famous jurist and founder of the Hanafite school of Muslim Law. For his life, see Shibli : *Sirat al-Nu'man* ; T. W. Juynboll's article on *Abu Hanifa* in *Ency. of Islam*, Vol. I, pp. 90-91.

10. *Dinar* : A gold coin of one *misqal* weight or ninety six barley grains. See Hussey : *Ancient Weights*.

11. A silver coin. Its weight has varied from time to time. See Blochman *Ain-i-Akbari*, p. 96.

12. '*Ushr* : Literally the term means the tenth or tithe. In Muslim States all cultivated land was classified as (a) '*Ushri*' (b) *Kharaji* and (c) *Sulhi*. '*Ushri* lands were (i) the lands of *Jazirat-ul-Arab* ; (ii) all lands whose owners accepted Islam and were left in possession of their estates ; (iii) all lands conquered by force and distributed among Muslim soldiers ; (iv) habitations of Muslims converted into gardens, provided they are irrigated with tithe water or alternately with '*Ushri* and *Kharaji* water ; (v) waste land, developed by Muslims.

The rate charged on '*Ushri* lands was one tenth for produce irrigated by rain or flood water and for wild fruits, the growing of which does not require great labour, one twentieth of the produce where the crops have to be irrigated with buckets or wheels, thus requiring extra labour. See *Hidayah* (translated by Hamilton), p.17. For a detailed discussion see Imam Yusuf : *Kitab-ul-Kharaj* (Bulaq edition 1302 A.H.) and Mawardi : *Ahkam-us-Sultaniya* (Cairo edition, 1909 A. D.). See also Grohmann's article on '*Ushr* in *Ency. of Islam*, Vol. IV pp. 1050-1052.

13. *Mawat-i-Ihya* : It means waste land brought into cultivation. Books on *Fiqh* have a chapter on *Ihya-ul-Mawat*, literally "making the dead soil alive". Land which is not being used is *Mawat*. Every Muslim who cultivates neglected land for himself becomes the proprietor of it, if it does not belong to another Muslim. According to most Muslim jurists express permission of the ruler is not necessary. Imam Abu Hanifa, however, considers it illegal to cultivate a *Mawat* without permission from the ruler. For details, *Kitab-ul-Kharaj* (Bulaq edition, 1302 A. H.) p. 36 *et seq* ; *Ahkam-us-Sultaniya*, p. 308 *et seq.*

14. *Mukatab* : The *Mukatab* is a slave who has obtained from his master the privilege of manumission on payment of a fixed price. Such slaves have the right to

engage in trade and buy and sell in order to earn the price of their freedom.

15. *Rabi crop* : the spring harvest ; sown in October and November and collected in the spring months (March-April).

16. *Sahibain* : A term used collectively for the two eminent disciples of Imam Abu Hanifa, viz., Imam Yusuf and Imam Muhammad.

17. *Ghanimah* : Means 'spoils of war.' Legally $\frac{1}{5}$ of the booty collected in a *ghazwa* should go to the State exchequer, the rest being equitably distributed among the soldiers. The portion which goes to the State exchequer is called *Khums*. See also Aghnides : *Mohammadan Theories of Finance*, p. 409 et seq. T. W. Juynboll's article on *Ghanima* in *Ency. of Islam*, Vol. II pp. 140-141 ; Lokkegaard, *Islamic Taxation in the Classical Period*, p. 42.

Khums : Literally the term means 'the fifth part'. Technically it means that portion of the booty which goes to the public exchequer. According to Muslim Law all booty should be collected, and a fifth set apart for the State, the rest being equitably distributed among the soldiers.

Firuz Shah writes in his *Futuhat* : "Hitherto it had been habitual and customary as the result of an innovation, that four-fifths of the spoils was brought into the *Diwan* and one-fifth given to the warriors. The *Shari'ah* on the other hand requires that one-fifth should be appropriated to the public treasury and four-fifths distributed amongst the warriors ; in this matter the injunctions had been completely reversed. If the distribution (of spoils) was not made according to the proportion fixed by the *Shari'ah* every appropriator of the spoils would be guilty of an illegal act, and children born of female captives, obtained by this means, would be bastards. In order to prevent this I ordered that one-fifth should be taken for the public treasury and four-fifths given to those who had seized the spoils" (*Futuhat-i-Firuz Shahi*, S. A. Rashid p. 17).

18. *Fay* : Literally means that which came back, in this instance, as Imam Shafi'i remarks, "that which God returned to His people (without fighting on their part), from those who opposed His religion," the theory implied being that property taken as spoils, as a matter of law, belongs to the Muslims. According to some *fay* means spoils taken without difficulty. According to Abu 'Ubaid, it is property taken from the enemy after the cessation of hostilities, such property belonging to all the Muslims. According to the *Mafatih* it is revenue derived from a country conquered by force.

According to 'Ali Ibn 'Isa, *fay* is more general than *ghanimah*, applying to everything. Finally, according to the *Misbah*, it is the *Kharaj* and the spoils. See also Aghnides, *Mohammadan Theories of Finance*, p. 425.

19. *Radhkh* : The combatants in a holy war are entitled to $\frac{4}{5}$ of the booty. Non-combatants are entitled to such a share as the leader may decide. This is known as *Radhkh*.

20. *Imam Hasan* (ob. 49 A. H.) was the eldest son of 'Ali and Fatima, the daughter of the Prophet. After the assassination of 'Ali, Hasan was proclaimed Caliph in Iraq, but he surrendered his claims to Amir Mu'awiya.

21. *Zufar* : Imam Zufar bin Huzail (ob. 115 A. H.). He was an eminent disciple of Imam Abu Hanifa.

22. *Dar-ul-Harb va Dar-ul-Islam* : In Muslim constitutional law the world is divided into *Dar-ul-Harb* and *Dar-ul-Islam*. The *Dar-ul-Islam* is a country where the ordinances of Islam are established and which is under a Muslim sovereign. *Dar-ul-Harb* is that country which is at war, actual or potential, with Muslims until by conquest it is turned into *Dar-ul-Islam*. See D. B. MacDonald's articles on *Dar-ul-Islam* and *Dar-ul-Harb* in *Ency. of Islam*, Vol. I, pp. 917-918.

23. *Battle of Badr* : The first battle of Badr was fought in the month of Ramzan A. H. 2 (March, 624 A. D.) between the Prophet and the Quresh. Many of the principal men of the Quresh tribe, including Abu Jahl, were slain in this battle. The battle of Badr is a turning point in the history of Islam. After it the Prophet began to build up the structure of the Republic of Medina.

24. *Riqaz* : The word *riqaz* means any property buried underground, whether by God, as the mine (*ma'dan*) or by man, as treasure trove (*Kanz*). According to *Hidayah*, *riqaz* means literally only a mine. The dispute on the meaning of the word *riqaz* has an important bearing because, as al-Qastallani observes in case *riqaz* means treasure trove alone, mines would be exempt from the tax of one-fifth. See also *Mohammadan Theories of Finance* p. 414 *et seq.*

25. *Zimmi* : According to Muslim Law, on the conquest of a non-Muslim country by Muslims, the population which does not embrace Islam and which is not enslaved is guaranteed life, liberty and property on promise of payment of *jizyah*, is called *Ahl-i-Zimma* or *Zimmis*, "People of the covenant or obligation." See *Ahkam-us-Sultaniya* (Cairo, 1298 A. H.) p. 121 *et seq.*, also D. B. MacDonald's article on *Dhimma* in *Ency. of Islam*, Vol. I pp. 958-959.

26. *Imam Yusuf* : Yaqub bin Ibrahim bin Habib al-Kufi (731-798) was a Hanafite jurist. He was appointed Qazi of Baghdad a post which was held by him till his death. His book on land tax (*Kitub-ul-Kharaj*), printed in Bulaq 1302 A. H. is considered an authority on the subject.

27. *Kharaj* : A tax on land. The term was originally applied to land tribute from non-Muslim tribes (*Hidayah*, Vol. II p. 204), but is now used for a tax, or land rent due to the State. Muslim writers divide *Kharaj* into two kinds (i) *Kharaj-i-Wazifa* and (ii) *Kharaj-i-Muqasimah*. The first term is applied to a demand in money and fixed on particular areas according to the kind of crops grown. Where a stipulated proportion of the produce is taken, it is called *Kharaj-i-Muqasimah*.

See also Th. W. Juynboll's article on *Kharaj* in *Ency. of Islam*, Vol. II pp. 902-903.

28. *Imam Muhammad* : Mohammad Ibn-ul Hasan, a pupil of Abu Hanifa, who died in 189 A. D.

29. *Imam Shafi'i* : Imam Abu Abdullah Muhammad bin Idris al-Shafi'i (767-820) was the founder of the *Shafi*, School of Law. For biographical details, see Heffening's article *al-Shafi'i* in *Ency. of Islam*, Vol. IV pp. 252-254.

30. *Imam Malik* : Abu Abdullah Malik bin Anas ibn Malik (ob. 179 A.H.) was the founder of the Malikite School of Law. His book *Kitab-ul-Muwatta* is the earliest, surviving law book. For biographical details, see J. Schacht's article *Malik bin Anas* in *Ency. of Islam*, Vol. III pp. 205-209.

31. *Amir-ul-Mominin 'Umar* : (ob. 644 A.D.), was the second Caliph of Islam. For his life, see Shibli, *Al-Faruq* (translated into English by Mawlana Zafar Ali Khan, Lahore) ; also *Encys of Islam*, G. Levi Della Vida's article, Vol. III pp. 982-984.

32. *Sa'a* : A measure for grains "of the value of 4 *mudd* (moduis) according to the custom of Medina" (*Lisan*). The word occurs in the Quran (Surah xii, 72) for the drinking cup placed by Joseph in his brother's pack. The Muslim jurists give the value of the *Sa'a* as 26-2-3 *riil*, the *riil* being equivalent to 128 Meccan drams and the dram weighing 50-2/5 grains of barley. See also Alfred Bel's article on *Sa'a* in *Ency. of Islam*, Vol. IV. p. 2.

33. *Jarib* : A measure chain or rope ; a land measure of 60 *gaz* square.

34. *Jiziyah* : A tax levied on non-Muslims (*Ahl-i-Zimma*) living in a Muslim State. It is founded on a direct injunction of the Quran, ix : 29. Military service was theoretically compulsory on all Muslims ; the non-Muslims could not be forced to perform military service. Hence this tax was realised on a cash equivalent of the assistance which they would be liable to give if they had not persisted in their unbelief because living as they do in the Muslim State they must be ready to defend it. (Aghnides : *Muhammadan Theories of Finance*, p. 399). *Jiziyah* was not imposed on those non-Muslims who fought with the Muslim armies. Women, children, priests, insane persons and beggars were exempt from it. The Sultans of Delhi charged 10, 20 and 40 *tankas* per annum per head according to the financial position of the person. (Afif, *Tarikh-e-Firoz Shahi*, p. 383).

35. *Sahib-i-Nisab* : A legal term for one possessed of a certain property upon which *zakat* must be paid.

36. *Najran* : Najran was a district in Northern Yemen. At the time of the advent of the Prophet, Jews, and Christian and pagan tribes lived there. These tribes sent an embassy to the Prophet, who concluded a treaty with them. According to this treaty these tribes were guaranteed the possession of their property and the free exercise of their religion in return for a fixed contribution on their part. This treaty was confirmed by Abu Bakr and 'Umar.

37. *Bani Taghlib* : An Arab tribe which, at the time of the rise of Islam, was occupying a province in Mesopotamia and professed the Christian faith. The *Bani Taghlib* sent an embassy to the Prophet who gave them complete religious freedom.

38. *Rum* : Rum stands for the Byzantine territory.

39. *Ahl-i-Harb* : People living in a country with which the Muslims are at war.

40. Tax levied on merchandise—The tax levied from Muslims was one half of the tax levied from non-Muslims.

41. *Ijarah* : "A fixed share of income, taking no heed of the eventual amount of output. It is considered as a case of sale of non-existing goods because the benefits from the use of the object leased accrue only in the future." See Lokkegaard, *Islamic Taxation in the Classical Period* p. 174; Aghnides, *Mohammadan Theories of Finance* p. 95.

42. *Muzariah* is an agreement between the owner of a farm and a farmer that the latter shall cultivate the farm in consideration of a certain proportion of the produce. It is also called *Mukhabarah*. The term *Muzariah* applies to the cultivation of grains, while the term *mu'amlah* and *musaqat* are used with respect to trees. *Mudarabah* is the counterpart of the same idea with respect to trade, meaning a partnership between the principal (*rabb-al-mal*), who owns the stock and the trader (*mudarib*), who contributes the labour for a part of the profits.

43. *Musaqat* : A contract between two persons, by which it is agreed that one shall deliver over to the other his fruit trees, on condition that the other shall take care of them, and whatever is produced shall belong to them both, in such proportions as may be stipulated. See *Hidayah*, Vol. IV, p. 54. Hughes : *Dictionary of Islam*.

44. For a detailed account of the functions of the officers of the Ministry of Revenue, see *The Administration of the Sultanate of Delhi* by Dr. Ishtiaq Husain Qureshy. *Tarikh-i-Firoz Shahi* of Shams Siraj Afif contains interesting passages about the duties and relations of the officers with each other. Two passages are translated here :

(a) "On receiving the officer of Ashraf-i-Mamalik in Firoz Shah's reign, Ain-ul-Mulk occupied his seat in the Ministry and began to discharge his duties with great

zeal, checking the account of the *maqtas*. But, under Divine will, differences arose between him and Khan-i-Jahan, the Minister, several times. Due to the immense bitterness that existed between them, they passed sarcastic remarks against each other. Their quarrel reached such a pitch that while they occupied their seats of office in front of the door of the palace, they freely indulged in raillery and exchanged insolent remarks ; their altercation exceeded all bounds. One day, while discussing the duties of Ashraf, the Minister said to Ain-ul-Mulk, "What has the Mushrif got to do with the register of expenditure, that he should take it into his head to demand those details from *maqtas*? The Mushrif is in charge of the income. The duty of verification of expenditure belongs to the Mustaafi". Ain-ul-Mulk retorted : "What concern has the Mustaafi with the detailed register of income ?" Both went, debating and exchanging abusive language, before the Sultan to seek his decision regarding the duties of the Mushrif and the Mustaafi ; Sultan Firoz thereupon ordered to the effect that the *maqtas* and other officers of the empire be instructed to furnish the details of income and a brief account of expenditure to the Ishraf office, details of expenditure and a summary of income to the Istifa office and details of both income and expenditure to the office of the Ministry. From that time upto this day that rule of Sultan Firoz has obtained in the Ministry ; while before that under the former Sultan, the officers used to send detailed descriptions (both of income and expenditure) to all the offices".

— (Afif ; pp. 408-410).

(b) "When Khan-i-Jahan sat on the Ministerial *masnad*, Nizamul-Mulk Amir Husain Amir-i-Amiran, who was Deputy Minister, sat on the immediate left of the *masnad*. Below the Deputy Minister sat the Mushrif-i-Mamalik. Below him sat the Postmaster-General (Barid-i-Mamalik). The Mustaafi sat to the Minister's right. The writer has been informed that the Mustaafi had always occupied the seat below the Mushrif. But when Muhammad, Sultan Muhammad (Tughlaq's) daughter's son, who had one brother, Maudud, received the office of Istifa and the title of Aziz-ul-Mulk in Firoz Shah's reign, the Sultan observed : 'Aziz-ul-Mulk is the daughter's son of my late master. How can he sit below the Mushrif ! And if I seated him above the Mushrif, it would be opposed to the custom established by former kings !' Sultan Firoz Shah, under Divine inspiration, commanded that as all the officers of the Ministry sat on Khan-i-Jahan's left, Aziz-ul-Mulk should sit on his right. When Sultan Firoz held his court, the Mustaafi stood above the Mushrif ; the Nazir and the Wuquf, with all the subordinate staff stood behind the Deputy Minister. It has been related that the post of Wuquf did not exist in former times. When Sultan Jalaluddin Khilji ascended the throne of Delhi, he reorganised the administration. He had a relation, who helped him in political matters and whom he was anxious to offer some office in the Ministry. On enquiry it was found that there was no vacancy in that office. The Minister suggested that if the Sultan was so pleased to command, one of the officers might be dismissed and the place thus vacated offered to that person. But the Sultan said that it was not right to dismiss a man without fault. As the Minister had perceived that the king's pleasure was that a place should be given to his relation among the officers (of the Ministry), he created the post of Wuquf for him. The duty of the Nazir was to scrutinize the account of receipts submitted by the officers of the empire to the office of Ishraf ; Wuquf checked the account of disbursements. Since the time of Sultan Jalaluddin Wuquf and Assistant Wuquf have been appointed among the officers of the Ministry. Should the duties of (all) the officers of the Ministry be recorded, a whole book would be required. How wise was the Minister of Sultan Jalal-ud-din ! What an office did he create ! . . . Firoz Shah also had a Minister of that calibre. (As he was there to carry on the administration, he never failed in the discharge of his duties. He maintained law and order in the country, putting down all disorders.)

— (Afif, pp. 419-421).

45. *Barid* : The purpose of the *Diwan-i-Barid* was "to enable the rulers to obtain quick information from everywhere and to transmit their orders as quickly as possible."

They were also required to satisfy the rulers' financial and commercial needs.

The word *barid* according to G. Sarton is not an original Arabic word nor is it of Persian origin. It is derived from Latin *veredus*, post-horse, courier's horse ; *veredorius*' courier.

For the sake of comparison see description of the Mongol postal services in the Yule-Cordier edition of Marco Polo (1,433-38 ; 11,480, 1926 ed).

